

From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy

Consultation Report

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1. Introduction

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are essential to achieve the goals of the European Green Deal and those of the global UNFCCC Paris Agreement. While much focus to date has been on the environmental or social benefits of NBS, less attention has been paid to their economic potential and their role in a just transition to the type of sustainable economy.

Systemic transformation is needed to shift towards the kind of economy envisaged in the European Green Deal where economic growth is decoupled from resource usage, industry is decarbonised and climate neutral, and all members of society are engaged in this transition in a fair and equitable way.

To achieve this systematic transformation, disruptive change is required. Change towards a **nature-based economy** where the value of nature in economic processes is recognised and measured, where the use of natural resources is reduced and restored, and where the diversity of actors involved in the production and consumption of nature are engaged in decision making processes about how nature should be used.

1.1 Draft White Paper for consultation

The draft White Paper for consultation *From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy*¹ ([download here](#)) proposes a paradigm shift regarding the economic potential of nature and recommends a series of transformative change actions and immediate actions to boost the nature-based economy.

This report provides an overview of the consultation process and results of the draft White Paper *From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy*.

The White Paper was prepared by the Nature-based Economy Working Group of Task Force III of the European Commission. Task Force 3 on “Governance, Business Models and Financial Mechanisms” aims to support and accelerate private sector uptake of NBS, and stimulate private sector investment in NBS, to move in the direction of an inclusive nature-based economy that creates new business opportunities and green employment (especially in light

¹ McQuaid, S., Rhodes, M.L., Andersson, T., Croci, E., Feichtinger-Hofer, M., Grosjean, M., Lueck, A. E., Kooijman, E., Lucchitta, B., Rizzi, D., Reil, A., Schante, J. (2021) *From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy - Delivering the Green Deal for Europe*. Draft White Paper for consultation. Nature-based Economy Working Group of EC Task Force III on Nature Based Solutions.

of post-COVID-19). The members of this task force come from academia, policy and practice and are representatives of EU funded projects undertaking research and demonstration in the financing, governance and business models of NBS. Contributions to the Working Group come from eleven Horizon 2020 projects and one LIFE project².

1.2 Aim of the consultation

The aim of the consultation process of the draft White Paper *From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy* was to get feedback from practitioners and experts, specifically on:

- The Nature-Based Economy concept;
- The market for nature-based solutions, in different sectors, geographies, and from different perspectives;
- Market barriers and enablers, and recommendations to overcome and support these.

This document provides an overview of the consultation process, an analysis of the stakeholder groups engaged, and a summary of the responses and feedback received from the different consultation activities. It will form the basis for the EC Expert Publication *The vital role of Nature-Based Solutions in the Nature Positive Economy*³([download here](#))..

2. Consultation Process

The consultation process towards the EC Expert Publication on the Nature-Based Economy consisted of the following steps:

1. Consultation process launched at international policy event on 29th June 2021
2. Consultation closed on 30th October 2021
3. Responses collated and analysed in November - December 2021
4. Overview of consultation results presented and discussed with the Task Force III Working Group (authors & contributors to the draft White Paper *From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy*) in January 2022
5. Actions taken in response to issues recorded in February – March 2022
6. Preparation of the EC Expert Publication *The vital role of Nature-Based Solutions in the Nature Positive Economy* with consideration of consultation input in February – March 2022

² For a list of projects with descriptions, see [Acknowledgements](#)

³ McQuaid, S., Kooijman, E., Rizzi, D., Andersson, T. and Schanté, J. (2022) *The vital role of Nature-Based Solutions in the Nature Positive Economy*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. [DOI:10.2777/307761](https://doi.org/10.2777/307761)

2.1 Types of responses

The consultation process consisted of two parts:

1. Online consultation (29 June 2021 – 30 October 2021)

- Publicly available on Network Nature
- Communication in newsletters and on social media of projects involved
 - Shared with members of Network Nature, Oppla, UrbanByNature, Connecting Nature Enterprise Platform

2. Direct feedback

- Feedback from events
- Experts, e.g. from academia, European Commission
- Practitioners, e.g. the Community ambassadors of the Connecting Nature Enterprise Platform
- TNO global roundtable 'How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy?'

2.2 Methodology for analysis

The consultation process consisted of an online questionnaire and a direct feedback option. In the online process, respondents had to answer a set of questions with predefined answers. In most cases, the respondents were asked to rank statements and / or recommendations on their importance or relevance. Here, respondents also had the option to add detailed comments and submit relevant documents related to the topic. For the direct feedback, we asked experts and practitioners. We also presented the report to the public at numerous events, and gave all participants the opportunity to ask questions and provide feedback.

After the consultation was closed and all the feedback was gathered, the first results of the online consultation process were presented in a meeting of the Nature-based Economy Working Group of Task Force III of the European Commission. It was found that this quantitative data only provided limited insights – it mainly showed us that respondents agreed with the measures and recommendations we proposed in the consultation process. The feedback to each of the questions, however, provided us with more qualitative data. Therefore, the working group decided to take all responses – both from the online consultation and the direct feedback - together for coding using a grounded theory approach. This allowed us to analyse responses in a structured and unbiased manner, as the coding of the responses uses a bottom up approach.

A collaborative working group approach to coding the responses into categories was carried out for the analysis of the unstructured results of the consultation process. In each of the online coding sessions, the authors of this report participated, together with 1 or 2 contributors. In the first round of coding, there 22 categories were identified, after which the authors looked

at overlaps between categories and merged categories into 8 final categories (of which 1 category has 4 subcategories). More information about the categories can be found in [Section 3.5](#).

2.3 Target stakeholder groups

The target stakeholder groups to respond to the consultation are:

- Policy makers at global, European, national and local government level
- Practitioners – nature-based enterprises delivering nature-based solutions
- Innovation ecosystem actors – business support agencies
- Investors
- Businesses

The consultation process was aimed at policy makers at all levels of government and across all fields of policy implementation. Particularly, the process aims to stimulate cross-sectoral policy dialogues between policy makers responsible for climate change and/or biodiversity policy and those responsible for sustainable economic growth policies within the context of rapidly depleting stocks of natural capital. The recommendations of the White Paper provide a basis for dialogue with wider stakeholders in business, society, the investment community and the innovation ecosystem on the changes needed to shift towards a Nature-Based Economy.

3. Results of the Consultation Process

3.1 Number of respondents

In total 170 responses were gathered through a structured online questionnaire (107), which included 113 comments from 75 respondents, and from direct feedback (63) gathered at organised roundtable discussions and events.

- Online consultation on Network Nature, number of respondents: 107 (see Table 1 and [Section 3.3](#))
 - Of which 75 responses included comments. Total of 113 comments.
- Direct feedback, number of responses: 63 (see Table 2 and [Section 3.4](#))
 - From 9 events and the TNOC Roundtable ‘How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy?’

3.2 Stakeholder representation

Figure 1 Respondents per stakeholder group and per continent, for the online consultation and the direct feedback, and the countries with the most respondents for both.

3.3 Online consultation

This section provides an overview of the results of the online questionnaire on the NBS market ([section 3.3.1](#)) and on recommendations for policymakers ([section 3.3.2](#)). The comments from respondents are included for each question.

Table 1 Questions from the online consultation process, the number of respondents and comments

Question	No. of respondents*	No. of comments
1. What measures supporting NBS market development are most important?	80-82	9
2. What nature-based activities have the most potential to generate economic activity?	61-64	10
3. What measures are needed to stimulate market demand for NBS?	58-63	11
4. What type of measures are most important to improve supply of NBS?	58-60	8
5. How important are nature based solutions in your country?	51	51
6. Prioritise specific recommendations from the White Paper for global policy makers.	12-17	4
7. Prioritise specific recommendations from the White Paper for EU policy makers.	7-12	3
8. Prioritise specific recommendations from the White Paper for national policy makers.	13-23	16

* As each question has a number of statements, the number of respondents per question could vary

3.3.1 NBS market

1. What measures supporting NBS market development are most important?

What measures supporting NBS market development are most important?

Rank from 1 (most important) to 5 (least important)

Feedback	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
Standardization and better calculability	-	- Standards
Deciding who is gonna pay - incentivizing cash flow into NBS following existing examples like through taxes or water supply fees, electricity fees, legislations addressing the polluter pays principle, etc.	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal
Quality standards & skills are already available although not in quantity but important to harness private awareness & investment so that they grow hand in hand	Nature-based enterprise	- Standards - Awareness – Private Sector
Make greening buildings part of the building and development plan of a city: - Connect greening buildings to wastewater reuse - Connect the bioeconomy to decentralised and connected green infrastructure and organic waste management	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges
Letting the whole market know about the full potential of the NBS for their sectors is also of huge importance. If an enterprise doesn't know about NBS, it won't invest in any solution of that sort.	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Private Sector - Case studies
Carbon credits for NBS is an important incentive: that can be bought OR of the voluntary carbon market OR linked to the EU ETS. Public funding should go to monitoring mechanism: sampling and modeling to know the overall carbon storage	Other private sector enterprise	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Carbon market
Incentive system	Other private sector enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal
Information campaigns for public workers and administrators , tools for implementing NBS in planning tools and in cities	Civil society/NGO	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Awareness – Public sector
Strategic incentives for citizens to exchange their land (when located in an environmentally sensitive area) with other plots located elsewhere would be a good practice as it would allow for NBS to be applied to the env sensitive areas more freely.	Individual	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal

2. What nature-based activities have the most potential to generate economic activity?

What nature-based activities have the most potential to generate economic activity?

Feedback	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
Natural capital accounting feels medium, but at the same time undeniably important to discover and probe for new economic possibilities and the creation of a sector where cash flow is substantial to maintain itself.	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial services e.g. natural capital accounting - Economic opportunities / challenges
It highly depends on three things: location, because politics and policies change from place to place; culture, which determines the people (stakeholders, politicians and civil society in general) willingness to engage and invest in NBS; and economics, which involves the capacity to invest in NBS and the kinds of solution they are going to prioritize.	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Location - economic situation - capacity to invest - Location - culture - citizen willingness to engage and invest
UN recognises Wellness tourism as top reason people will travel internationally & Ireland is in a unique place to harness this welcoming small groups to relatively unspoilt environment not saturated with visitors centres & the like.	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Economic opportunities/challenges - Location - economic situation - capacity to invest - Location - natural environment influences potential for health & wellbeing tourism
There is some developer on smart metering and sensoring. Most financial value is combination of carbon storage and replacing fossil based material with NBS material	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal
To be integrated into a "landscape" approach, a "territorial" planification and development. It means that the synergies and coherence between several sectorial approaches must be considered as a criteria and priority.	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation
Urban deployment of NBS for food production, water management, energy and education would all create new jobs and new opportunities, bringing additional wealth to local economies and our national GDP.	Public sector organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges
NBS have a big potential in climate change adaptation actions in cities	Civil society/NGO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach

		- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration
I valued low those activities that may have high economic impact for few companies/actors/individuals already on the market when compared with solutions that overall would create many more jobs and therefore new enterprises, innovative services and trigger real societal change	Civil society/ NGO	- System change
Upgrade of existing and development of new infrastructure using the NBS approach is the key to maximise the economic benefits.	Academic/ Research institute	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges
Water management and food production will be the biggest issues we will need to face and NBS may lead the way	Individual	- Economic opportunities/challenges

3. What measures are needed to stimulate market demand for NBS?

What measures are needed to stimulate market demand for NBS?

Feedback	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
Mandatory valuation is highly important as the technological means exist to process massive data, and the data can be used by environmental economists.	Nature-based enterprise	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Economic opportunities / challenges
Integration into all fields of the economy	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - System change
we urgently need to monetize Eco System Services of NBSs	Nature-based enterprise	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - System change
public administrations have to adopt NBS in their territories as stimulus for private investments .	Civil society/NGO	- Case studies
Legislation	Civil society/NGO	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal
Also, involving the general population would make them ask for more focus from the government in NBS for both private and public sectors. The more people recognizing its importance the higher demand for the adoption of NBS will be.	Academic/Research institute	- Awareness - Citizens / Third sector
A straightforward and transparent marketing strategy could be implemented, to make citizens familiar and understand the need for NBS and how much different their lives can be once NBS are put to action. Transparency in the financial side of these investments is mandatory.	Individual	- Awareness - Citizens / Third sector
Examples of existing projects based on NBS, where it's easy to understand their benefits. A report itself of many examples	Individual	- Case studies
Master planning of land uses and enablers of regulatory framework to ensure the impacts NBS will have (and not measured by small scale projects)	-	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach
Example: the green up of existing on buildings (rooftops , Façade , offices etc. will be an expense to the owner and user without immediate benefit. Long-term it will benefit owner	-	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation

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<p>and society as a whole. Immediate tax incentives for investment or financial benefits to carbon offsets would make investments way more attractive to building owners (on top of all other positive benefits that directly contribute to the owner of buildings, such as reduced maintenance cost on Façade and roof, reduced energy cost etc)</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy
<p>standardisation, NBS typologies, certification</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>- Standards</p>

4. What type of measures are most important to improve supply of NBS?

What type of measures are most important to improve the supply of NBS?

Feedback	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
The biggest immediate effect would be supporting existing businesses which already deliver NBS - they have the skills and knowledge but need to scale up. The limiting factor is often the management of the company, usually former experts themselves who are not born business people and therefore scale slower and more carefully. Assist them in scaling up, and you'll get more output. The demand is big enough.	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments economic policy - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building
Incentives for the emergence of new suppliers of NBS products would also make the suppliers themselves invest time, energy and money into network events, publicity about NBS, offering more types of solution services, R&D, and job positions.	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments economic policy - Economic opportunities / challenges
In Germany the RAL Gütezeichen has recently become available regarding quality standards: https://www.ral-vertikalbegruendung.de/	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards
Link carbon credits to EU ETS and to meeting national CO2 targets	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Carbon market
To simplify and make cheaper access to NBS related to climate mitigation (AFOLU carbon offsets methodologies)	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Carbon market - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments cross policy collaboration
regulation has an important role for supply NBS projects by professionals	Civil society/NGO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards
Access to funding is one of the most common barriers to NBS implementation. Governments can attract such investments and increase the market demand by modifying and re-orienting their policies, subsidies, and public investments and provide better incentives for private investors to finance adaptation projects. Procurement, financing conditions, industry standards, and other policies should be improved to ensure that NBS are included and evaluated among the various adaptation solutions and their benefits are assessed for all options under consideration.	Academic/Research institute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments economic policy
See IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions for more details on "quality standards related to NbS"	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards

5. How important are nature based solutions in your country? (Open question)

Feedback	Country	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
They (NBS) have become part of the Vienna building strategy Other than that, they are not yet connected to the bioeconomy nor necessarily to wastewater reuse - greywater has been mentioned though	Austria	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges
Plenty of opportunities to implement NBS, but given that we are in an arid climate with limited water resources available, it is more challenging. However, we can help cool down cities, generate liveable space etc, if we put in strategic efforts into decentralised water treatment, water reuse and sound landscape planning using native a draught tolerant plant species.	Bahrain	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Location - natural environment
very important - desealing actions with citizens, combination with co-creation approaches strengthening commitment and buy-in plus ownership; expanding green corridors	Belgium	Civil society/NGO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector - Co-creation/ Participatory approaches - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
Nature Climate Solutions shows the greatest potential and the right bet in Brazil, fostering green finance to help the World on the mitigation challenge.	Brazil	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location - economic situation
Considering that Brazil has the highest level of biodiversity in the world and the necessity of preserving it, the country is a hotspot for ecological engineering solutions. This huge biodiversity can generate royalties from existing biological solutions, R&D investments, provisions for the carbon market, and many others. The stimulus to focus on nature usage for making and saving money from the family level (in ecological agriculture, controlled extractivism, art, tourism, etc) to the industrial level (by saving money from solid waste and wastewater management,	Brazil	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment - System change

monitoring a product lifecycle, energy and light sources, better working conditions, etc) and the public sector (being able to invest less money in environmental sanitation, environmental health, fixing damaged infrastructure due to extreme climate events and build expensive short-to-mid longevity ones, etc, and investing it in other sectors) in Brazil would solve many socioeconomic issues that the country faces, like socioeconomic inequalities, loss of environmental quality and forest area, stimulate environmental consciousness by a large range of the society, promote more resources like fresh water and, since it is a hydropower energy-based country, more electricity capacity, bring more financial investment from abroad and many other benefits.			
Increasingly important	Brazil	Nature-based enterprise	-
Brazil has a great potential for NBS that needs to be stimulated to reverse the current environmental issues, not only in natural areas, but also to enhance and transition the dense and problematic built environment of cities.	Brazil	Academic/Research institute	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal
NbS should be important in every country. At present NbS in Bulgaria are quite misused.	Bulgaria	Nature-based enterprise	- Standards - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector
In Canada, NBS is only beginning to be appreciated. Treatment wetlands have been designed for 30 years, but the design and acceptance of other ecosystems that provide services is no more than 10 years old.	Canada	Nature-based enterprise	- Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Location - natural environment
Their importance for my country is immense. However, the current policies and the existing ideology of using resources only for making money as fast as possible is a significant barricade to the enhancement of NBS. The main issues currently running in my country, which can be solved/mitigated by NBS, are: desertification, coastal erosion, overextraction of groundwater, lack of farming practice diversification, increasing air pollution, overexploitation of resources for economic purposes and declining biodiversity.	Cyprus	Individual	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - economic situation - Location - natural environment - System change
This answer is aimed to connect the white paper with the EMME Climate Change initiative of the Republic of Cyprus, which aims to design a coordinated approach to climate change mitigation and adaptation in the East Mediterranean and Middle East region, including 17 countries. The area is a hotspot for the climate change and NBS appear as a strategic tool for facing the climate change in a region with a limited biocapacity, which has been further declining in the last decades. From the regeneration of water cycles, to the mitigation of heat islands in the cities, NBS represent a way to achieve the exponential change that is required. NBS can also match the combined goal of improving the environmental conditions while generating new businesses and job opportunities in countries that are characterised by a high level of unemployment.	Cyprus	Academic/Research institute	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment - System change
Popular topic with all political parties, healthy and relatively skilled business environment but lack of awareness among ordinary people. For more info see reports at zelenestrechy.info.	Czech Republic	Nature-based enterprise	- Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector

Better calculability, standardization would be important. NBS feel important and needed in several sectors in both countries, e.g. water quality, green buildings etc. have large potential and in some cases, good social acceptance.	France	Nature-based enterprise	- Standards - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
They're important but they're not always implemented due to several reasons: - scepticism/low understanding of consulting companies that make public project recommendations - Inertia of companies to change their practices (construction companies...) - No of mandatory implementation of NBS when possible - Presence of "older" generations of politicians that have not yet understood the urgency of climate change and conduct policies of "business as usual"	France	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector
Very important! on a corporate level there is hardly any knowledge but the willingness to learn and invest.	Germany	Nature-based enterprise	- Awareness – Private sector
Huge, with the right change of Regulation and policies	Germany	-	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Economic opportunities / challenges
Quite important and increasing. Most important aspect I see is water/irrigation provision for all the greening. This will be THE main issue soon...keyword "sponge city"..."Schwammstadt"	Germany	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Economic opportunities / challenges
The importance of NBS is increasing steadily (even if it could be more).	Germany	Other private sector enterprise	
The potential for NBS in Greece is really huge. For the simplest application, ie water and wastewater management, more than 85% of settlements and communities with population smaller than 2000 people do not have proper sanitation services. Considering also the hundreds of islands, extensive mountainous inland and many rural areas, the decentralized NBS approach can deal with this issue. Moreover, more than 70% of the population leaves already in urban environments, hence NBS infrastructure is necessary to improve the liveability and ecosystem services in the urban context. Also, Greece is already suffering from climate change impacts; desertification is already noticed in the southern islands, extreme weather events are becoming more frequent and intense (eg heat waves) and many areas (eg islands) are already suffering by limited availability of freshwater resources. NBS can be the way to deal with these pressing issues in the Greek economic and social context.	Greece	Academic/Research institute	- Location - natural environment

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Extremely important, in fact a lot more important than the majority of our public realizes. Even though Hungary is not currently at the forefront of bearing the negative effects of climate change and biodiversity loss, the indirect cascading effects will eventually reach such countries like ours with a temperate climate and landlocked geographic. We do need to make every effort to combine conservation, protecting, restoring and regenerating natural ecosystems with greening our cities to make them healthier, less polluted, more resilient and connected to nature!	Hungary	Nature-based enterprise	- Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector
NBS are important but currently very little public or private investment organised. Many small groups working in their own areas/sectors but media emphasis is overall low key & no almost acknowledgment from government, medical or educational sectors as to the benefits. The potential is huge.	Ireland	Nature-based enterprise	- Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector
There is an increasing awareness of their importance. They are very important, we are a small country with fantastic access to natural resources and beautiful landscapes. NBS will become even more important in the next 5-10 years. We need to preserve the natural environment for the current and future generations.	Ireland	Nature-based enterprise	- Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment
Extremely important - particularly related to wind / water-based solutions and restoration of peat bogs	Ireland	Academic/Research institute	- Economic opportunities / challenges
NBS are increasing in importance in Ireland - local authorities are actively implementing NBS measures since COVID - parklets, pocket parks, improved green spaces etc. Large scale measures like SUDS, green buildings and roofs etc are slowly increasing but cost is a major factor. Also lack of awareness of NBS suppliers and issues such a rigid public procurement processes hinder the growth of the market	Ireland	Other private sector enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public procurement - Economic opportunities / challenges
in my country there is a little knowledge of NBS , we have to improve professionals and public offices skills, in public offices there are not skills and sensitiveness to this issue.	Italy	Civil society/NGO	- Awareness – Public sector
Italy is one of the most biodiverse country in Europe and we long-lived of agropastoral activities run by families or small to medium enterprises. Similarly to France, we still use many low-tech high-impact solutions and if seen from a NBS perspective, historically, we were amongst the most resilient societies. Recently intensive agriculture and herding (pushed by our be-headed capitalistic system) and a poor awareness of environmental damage done by fertilizers and chemicals, is depleting our soils and traditional NBS. It's fundamental to protect, revive, enhance and promote those solutions that do not require too big investments in technological solutions that create few hyper specialized jobs, leaving too many humans and other species behind.	Italy	Civil society/NGO	- Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment - System change

<p>NBS could be striking innovation trend and sustainable development's enabler. Cities and green areas needs to become proactive agents for climate change adaptation, then NBS represent a paradigmatic shift where economical and socio-cultural resources are catalyzed. Italy that has a strong economic leverage on construction markets through public procurement needs to update design techniques and implementation process.</p>	<p>Italy</p>	<p>Other private sector enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Economic opportunities / challenges - System change
<p>Enormous. The Combination of environmental degradation, encroachment into sensitive water sources, upstream diversion, pollution of land and water in a rapidly growing population have devastated biodiversity and ecosystem services. Need for NBS to start to the restoration</p>	<p>Kenya</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>Very important but complex to strike a balance with spatial use and nitrogen and biodiversity matters</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>	<p>Other private sector enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Location - natural environment - System change
<p>The potential is large in the Netherlands as many industries are lacking or not using NBS , there is also a lack of proper standards and incentives to implement NBS from the private sector. I would say it is really important as many innovations here are not NBS based.</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
<p>Huge potential, but is important to articulate the public and private sector with local stakeholders and enhance local policies according and beyond the current National Environmental Policy to 2030.</p>	<p>Peru</p>	<p>Academic/Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Co-creation/ Participatory approaches - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration

So far, they are barely adopted. Not because there is lack of expertise or expert, but by lack of will by public decision makers. However, the potential is very high, from forestry to agriculture to urban development.	Portugal	Individual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Economic opportunities / challenges
Extremely important; have potentiality to develop clean/renewable energy	Qatar	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges
There is a national landscape architects association that promotes NBS in education and practice, however as a newly recognized job category there is low public investment in climate change adaptation, mitigation, and food security projects that would make use of NBS. Meanwhile the ample natural landscape degradation is shown by rivers drying and forests disappearing, with large investments leaving nature behind.	Romania	Civil society/NGO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
At public level - high At political level - medium or low	Romania	Civil society/NGO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector
Nature based solutions are getting on importance, taking into account the character and potential of the country in terms of availability of biomass and natural resources, changes in consumer behaviour towards nature-friendly solutions	Slovakia	Other private sector enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Public sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment
In my country, NBS have the same importance as in the rest of Europe and other developed countries, I mean, very high. If you take a walk around your neighbourhood you can see a lot of serious problems that would have been less important simply by applying some NBS criteria. But also in less urbanized countries, with less artificial infrastructures, it's very important to promote their development since its very beginning with NBS criteria, avoiding repeating mistakes of already developed countries (that must take steps back towards renaturalization and rewilding, there is no choice)	Spain	Public sector organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Awareness – Public sector - Location - natural environment
There is a big potential and a big need for NBS. More frequent and extreme droughts, heatwaves, hydric stress, lack of green in urban areas, air pollution, sea level rise or lack of social cohesion are some of the challenges that we are facing today and could be improved through the use of NBS.	Spain	Nature-based enterprise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment
Spain is facing climate change in first line, NBS can contribute to better water management in urban areas.	Spain	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment

I believe it depends on regions more than country level. In our country pretty low, in my region medium to low	Spain	Nature-based enterprise	- Location - natural environment
The concept, as everywhere else, it's still at its infancy, and even more its application via IUCN Global Standard for NbS. Yet, there is growing interest, and certainly a rapidly evolving conversation thanks to a couple of key actors, namely: IUCN-Med, NbS Observatory, and NbS Cluster. Also, there is a noticeable demand from large companies of carbon credits to finance NbS projects benefitting local communities. And lastly there are more and more city rewilding projects, especially concerning rivers, that seen through the NbS lens -applying IUCN Global Standard-, could be significantly enhanced in all dimensions, multiply impact and serve as inspiration for many others.	Spain	Nature-based enterprise	- Standards - Awareness – Public sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
The south of Spain will burn in the next 50 years due to climate change, high risk to become like the Sahara. Actually, already now in summer, the temperatures that Sevilla, Granada etc. reach are unbearable. NBSs will be indispensable for climate adaptation-mitigation measures if we do not want to live underground.	Spain	Civil society/NGO	- Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - natural environment
In Sweden the awareness level of NbS is relatively high among several stakeholders, However, more needs to done in order to capture the real potential, example of such initiatives could include the establishment of platforms (online and on-site) where supply and demand can meet.	Sweden	Academic/Research institute	- Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
My country is Syria and NBS is the best solution to handle the environment problem in such arid climate. So important.	Syria	Academic/Research institute	- Location - natural environment
In Ukraine, the nature-based approach to adaptation and strengthening of resilience recently started to emerge. Considering the very great level of land degradation, low share of protected areas, high need to adapt the climate-related hazards, nature-based solutions are part of the key solutions. Using of nature-based solutions is also included in the draft Environmental Security and Climate Change Adaptation Strategy of Ukraine by 2030 (currently under governmental consideration).	Ukraine	Academic/Research institute	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Location - natural environment
Nature based solutions need to be important in every country, however regulators and policy makers need to be educated and not adopt the same measures used for other regulatory and policy requirements. A lot more awareness needs to be reached	United Kingdom	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Public sector
Important, especially to address our carbon ambitions and address our biodiversity crisis.	United Kingdom	Civil society/NGO	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration
Very and increasingly so, especially with the Nature Recovery Networks and Environmental Land Management Schemes coming though.	United Kingdom	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
Awareness growing rapidly , a lot more needing done to facilitate practical implementation at scale with resources available . “How “ we work to do that with resource we have has taken thinking but that thinking is getting there .	United Kingdom	Public sector organization	- Economic opportunities / challenges
Scotland is making progress in its commitments	United Kingdom	Individual	
Extremely important. Under the Biden administration, the USA has a renewed sense of urgency behind approaches like NbS. As the climate crisis continues to worsen and effects continue to be felt, it is critical that NbS are applied in the USA - a country with substantial capital and expertise in the area of NbS and related approaches.	United States	Civil society/NGO	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy

3.3.2 Recommendations for policy makers

6. Specific recommendations for global policy makers

Recommendations for global policymakers

Feedback	Question	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
<p>The introduction of interdisciplinary training courses to enterprises and governments would be extremely important to equalize the knowledge and promote a state-of-the-art network of collaborations.</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
<p>The restoration of Earth and the restoration of humanity are sides of the same coin; they are intertwined and complementary and must be addressed simultaneously in space and time, for their mutual support. In this sense, advocacy, research and teaching programs must be carried out in view of an ecosystem approach, defining and dealing with the problems at the bottom of the pot, considering the general phenomenon, and not the bubbles on the surface, as we commonly see in segmented policies, reduced academic formats and mass media headlines. Ref.: PILON, A. F., Restoring the Relationship between People and the Earth: Environment, Politics and Governance / Restaurer les Relations entre les Hommes et la Terre: Environnement, Politique et Gouvernance [on line]: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353130658_Restoring_the_Relationship_between_People_and_the_Earth_Environment_Politics_and_Governance"</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Academic/ Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration - System change
<p>Convince more countries into participating in a global network and adopting NBS strategies, and also developing their own, is also very important.</p>	<p>Immediate actions to boost the NBS market</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
<p>Institutional capacity, judicial neutrality, informational transparency and social spaces for civic engagement and enlightened political participation are key factors to face the clashes between formal and informal institutions and elite agencies as critical junctures that lead to different outcomes. How to deal with the effects of the asymmetric power relationships between common people and corporations? How to preserve the values of populations rooted in specific niches, such as indigenous peoples, in view of the power of the economic, political and technological system, which imposes its worldview (the “productivity paradigm”), actively threatening their physical and cultural territories? Ref.: PILON, A. F., What changes are needed to face the global crisis? The Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES): https://onet.ipbes.net/node/48</p>	<p>Immediate actions to boost the NBS market</p>	<p>Academic/ Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation / Participatory approaches - System change

7. Specific recommendations for EU policy makers

Recommendations for EU policymakers

■ Not at all important
 ■ Somewhat important
 ■ Important
 ■ Extremely important

Feedback	Question	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
<p>Support SMEs on NBS development and policy making in order to make them (all) active users/contributors as soon as possible to have the end-users on board in order to create a much faster change (we may say a transformative change) then the usual top-down policy processes.</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Civil society/ NGO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Co-creation / Participatory approaches - System change
<p>More nature = more good and better for all as without it we will perish.</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Individual</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>NBS should be more actively part climate change mitigation plans, they can play a vital role in reducing the carbon footprint, especially when used at a large scale, i.e., across ecosystems and cities. Climate impact and vulnerability assessments should include analysis of impacts on ecosystems and the implications for people’s vulnerability. For this, planning, decision-making, and action on adaptation should follow a system perspective and NBS should be part of such plans from the beginning. Financial institutions should develop new funding streams and models that can support long-term investment in NBS for climate change adaptation, including private sector actors.</p> <p>As said, EU and national governments should re-orient policies, subsidies, and public investments and give better incentives for private investors to finance NBS projects. And of course, NBS should be integrated at all levels into financial conditions, ie procurement, industry standards, and other policies</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Academic/ Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Financial institutions

8. Specific recommendations for national policy makers

Recommendations for national policymakers

Not at all important Somewhat important Important Extremely important

Recommendations for national policymakers

Feedback	Question	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
<p>Governance of Urban G.I and NBS needs to be put on a statutory mandated basis, with obligations on regional and local government bodies to plan, design and manage Urban G.I and NBS. This issue seems ignored within Horizon 2020 funded projects. In most EU member states, the provision of expertise at local government levels is too low to ensure effective and coherent delivery of NBS to best practice standards. In Rep. of Ireland and U.K, the planning, design and management of Urban G.I and NBS as a function or service of local government is merely optional, not obligatory, leaving it in a very weak position, especially in the recent austerity years. In Rep. of Ireland, of the 31 local councils, only about 8 (it's difficult to get info.), have in-house expertise in Landscape Architecture, Arboriculture, Ecology or Greenspace Management, all vital disciplines for Urban GI and NBS. This must be addressed as a priority.</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Public sector organization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building
<p>Go by example and advertise it</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case studies
<p>A participatory model of governance of the NBS and even of the environment is pretty important. But to promote an NBE strategic plan implementation process it is far more important to make the population (civil and private sector) and the governmental bodies understand what it is about. Improving the educational sector to share knowledge about NBS and NBE has a higher priority. Without it, strategic plans would not work due to lack of acceptance: if people don't know what it is and why it is important, they are not willing to pay for it.</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector - Location - culture - citizen willingness to engage and invest - Co-creation / Participatory approaches
<p>Local and regional climate action plans, now mandatory in many parts of Europe, can serve as an ideal legal framework to mainstream NbS for climate action. The co-creation of such plans among all key stakeholders ensures proper governance of the measures comprised, including NbS initiatives.</p> <p>Local NbS incubators, where all key stakeholders take an active role, can act as hubs and multipliers of the nature-based economy. We're actually co-leading the development of one here in Malaga (southern Spain) together with IUCN-Med, the NbS cluster and the City Council's economic development agency.</p>	<p>Systemic change measures</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities / challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration - Case studies

Public sector , in partnership with private sector, should commission applied research in Urban NBS, for e.g. in Urban Forestry and Edible Landscapes	Measures to stimulate demand	Public sector organization	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
Reduce red tape, encourage small businesses	Measures to stimulate demand	Nature-based enterprise	-- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy
Increasing awareness about NBS and NBE and how they could benefit the population has incredible importance. The more people know about it and its cost-benefits, the higher the chance for them to accept and adopt it, which will raise the demand for NBS and NBE policies and products.	Measures to stimulate demand	Nature-based enterprise	- Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector - Location - culture - citizen willingness to engage and invest
The joint involvement of civil society, SMEs, academia and the media, together with local governments and large companies, all throughout the process of designing, implementing and maintaining NbS is key for its uptake, mainstreaming and long-term sustainability. To this end regular multi-stakeholder fora should be common practice.	Measures to stimulate demand	Nature-based enterprise	- Co-creation / Participatory approaches - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
Help existing businesses grow	Measures to stimulate private sector supply	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building
Not only addressing barriers but also supporting the production of national incentives to promote the local level stimulus of the NBS market sector and connecting both private and public sectors through partnerships. Since NBS somehow benefits the population in general, public and private sectors should be involved in the same networks and much as possible. Connecting the many government hierarchies in a multi-level sense with the local, regional and national NBS suppliers would help to deal with the lack or excess of services in some regions and also help to promote an even territorial NBE development.	Measures to stimulate private sector supply	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
Training on skills for NbS is of high importance at this early stage for all key stakeholders, including policy makers, but also professionals (especially the unemployed and vulnerable) seeking to enter the green economy, entrepreneurs, students, and the media, among others	Measures to stimulate private sector supply	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building

<p>The resources that SMEs may need to spend on providing specific accounting or valuation of their NBS (carbon...) can quickly be overwhelming and hinder their capacity to deploy NBS, opening the door to big corporate overtake of the NBS market...</p>	<p>Measures to address public procurement challenges</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy
<p>Procurement of NBS, as standalone or part of infrastructure projects, should remain based on evaluating the best value for money, taking into account the environmental and social benefits NBS can bring. Procurement processes and capacities of procurers needs to be geared towards that purpose, not towards specific new types of suppliers, because new types of suppliers will keep emerging and it is not possible for procurement processes to keep adjusting at the same pace as new suppliers and innovations enter the market. One key aspect is to ensure procurers/procurement agencies understand the importance using performance/outcome based procurement. That will help to scale up NBS.</p>	<p>Measures to address public procurement challenges</p>	<p>Civil society/NGO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public procurement - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building
<p>Reduce red tape</p>	<p>Measures to address public procurement challenges</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy
<p>I would recommend that the public sector develop the procurement process basing them at the local/regional scales, since the adoption of the same NBS strategies can respond differently, even negatively, for the different ecosystems in with they can be implemented. Also, some private markets could differently recognize NBE strategies, depending on their local/regional culture and model of business.</p>	<p>Measures to address public procurement challenges</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public procurement - Location - natural environment
<p>A dynamic interaction and fluent communication between NBEs and local governments would go a long way to facilitation a vibrant, local, nature-based economy</p>	<p>Measures to address public procurement challenges</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration

3.4 Direct feedback

Table 2 List of events where participants could provide direct feedback, and the number of responses received

Event	Date	No. of responses
Public presentation of the draft White Paper and High Level Policy Dialogue at the Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit	29 June 2021	9
Public presentation of the draft White Paper at the IUCN World Conservation Congress	7 September 2021	4
Presentation at the Climate Alliance Annual Congress	7 September 2021	3
Presentation at the UK Chartered Forestry Association	9 September 2021	4
Public presentation of the draft White Paper at Innovate4Cities	13 October 2021	4
Public presentation of the draft White Paper at Network Nature annual event	21 October 2021	1
Public presentation of the draft White Paper by the European Commission at the European Business and Nature Summit	30 November 2021	9
Connecting Nature Enterprise Platform Ambassador Feedback Session	15 December 2021	7
The Nature Of Cities Roundtable ' How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy? '	-	22

3.4.1 Feedback from events

Feedback	Event	Stakeholder group	Category (first round)
In the current economic system, we are spending more money in destroying nature than in protecting it. We need to transition to an economy that is restorative. For this, we need to change the perspective from the national level to land- and seascapes as the main economic assets, and cities as engines of change for nature and resilience. This requires disruption of traditional supply chains and approaches towards a truly 'green' economy and changing design, consumption and production. This is not just protecting nature, it is about accelerating the restorative economy as a driver of businesses of the future. Innovation, IT and generating jobs and investment opportunities in cities and regions means incubating, accelerating, financing and empowering youth to put nature and climate resilience into every cent we spend and invest, sharing all our knowledge and helping them build the new world we need urgently – putting money and work where our mouth is.	Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit	Public sector organisation	- System change - Financial institutions

<p>Nature can generate income and revenues and create jobs. Nature can directly generate an income by, for example, offsetting schemes, and increasing property value and retail purchases. But that is only part of the story. Globally, nature can unlock an estimated \$10 trillion of business opportunities and 395 million jobs by transforming economic systems WEF (2020) The Future Of Nature And Business Report). We need a radical shift away from current economic approaches towards a new perspective where nature is valued and recognised as an alternative path for economic development. Some cities are already starting to do this - Amsterdam has embraced Doughnut Economics and London is starting with biodiversity positive developments. However, to maintain green spaces in cities and generate revenue sustainably, people need to be trained. Value increase in property as a result of green spaces needs to be inclusive for people and nature-positive.</p>	<p>Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit</p>	<p>Public sector organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System change - Economic opportunities/challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches /local value creation
<p>And there are already sectors where this is happening. In Austria, for every 10th building being developed a green roof is being installed and 33,000 new jobs are being created. With targeted measures, policy goals for health, economy, energy and the environment could be combined and thus lead to a permanently effective economic engine. Because nature is essential and that recreational areas are important for our well-being, especially in the city. By addressing greening buildings in an urban setting we create added value for the buildings, the city and the people. But greening buildings is just a first step. We need forward-looking developments and integrated concepts for smart, resilient urban development to create green and liveable cities. Research and innovation is key in this, and cooperation between policy in energy, construction and greening is necessary to make climate protection accessible to everyone in a fair manner.</p>	<p>Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit</p>	<p>Public sector organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Economic opportunities/challenges
<p>The growth of the nature-based economy needs to be stimulated by developing public and private demand. We are also seeing the importance of the private sector in the supply chain of NBS. We see the need to boost their competencies through actions such as training, support for innovation etc. Networking is important and we're looking at NBE programmes to mobilise actors. The EU Taxonomy is important to boost investment in sustainable activities and nature-based enterprises. More investment is needed - both from the public and the private sector.</p>	<p>Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit</p>	<p>Public sector organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - carbon market - Financial institutions - Awareness – Private sector - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
<p>Nature-based enterprises are ready to deliver solutions, but we need to understand each other better (public - private collaboration) and work together more. In working with the public sector, there are difficulties in terms of procurement of NBS and the problem of silo-thinking. NBS are complex to implement, and policies need to be harmonized to enable implementation. Public procurement can be a powerful driver for nature-based solutions, and thus nature-based enterprises, but it is difficult to find opportunities, and see how NBS are included.</p>	<p>Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit</p>	<p>Nature-based enterprise</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - carbon market - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building
<p>Nature-based enterprises offer our young people alternative career paths – rewarding and highly skilled career paths– using science and technology to harness the potential of nature to combat climate change and biodiversity loss. There is a need to deliver the professionals for the future for</p>	<p>Connecting Nature</p>	<p>Public sector organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities/challenges

<p>these specific challenges requiring different skill sets, in particular interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary skills.</p> <p>Nature can induce and inspire entrepreneurial activities that with respect to nature can contribute to economic growth and job creation. As the city of Poznań we are well-known in Poland for our entrepreneurial business spirit especially when it comes to development of Small and Medium Enterprises. The role of our city is to create the best ecosystem for development of entrepreneurship – we are now creating such an ecosystem for nature-based enterprises. We deliver a series of trainings with the goal to upgrade the skills of entrepreneurs, and increase the knowledge and skills of our city employees and designers concerning nature-based solutions. This also means that we promote and implement NBS in our municipal activities. Starting with pilot initiatives, we are testing the use of nature-based solutions with designers and subcontractors. By doing this, we gain the necessary experience and skills of not only working with NBS, but also with the private sector and entrepreneurs.</p>	Enterprise Summit		- Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
<p>People need to be engaged in the nature-based economy and hear about the benefits. The climate and biodiversity crisis needs to be treated as a priority and this requires involvement of all stakeholders, including citizens and the private sector. For this, knowledge gaps need to be addressed. We know that there is huge potential, however NBS are complex and require tailor-made holistic approaches. We need to increase awareness about NBS and communicate the benefits for the economy, ecosystems and biodiversity, and climate change.</p>	Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit	Public sector organisation	- Awareness – Private sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector
<p>Warsaw takes good care of nature, and through our projects, we have demonstrated that nature too cares about us, bringing us benefits, including economic ones. This year we have implemented a pilot project involving the appraisal of tree ecosystem services. We learned that the air-cleaning, oxygen production and carbon dioxide storage services provided by trees in Warsaw alone are worth a whopping PLN 170 million a year (about EUR 37.69 million). This allowed us to launch a Green Fund, allowing the private sector to contribute to green projects across the city. The Fund aims to encourage businesses to support Warsaw’s development, and to build a sense of community and co-responsibility for the city’s space.</p>	Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit	Public sector organisation	- Case studies
<p>We need massive investment into nature to halt biodiversity loss. Solutions are ready to be implemented, but the policy framework is lagging behind. Local governments are key enablers that play an important role in supporting the development of the Nature-based economy, both in knowledge sharing and in providing dedicated regional support, including through smart specialisation. On the EU-level, we are supporting innovative projects where the nature-based skills of architects, engineers, scientists, designers, technical organisations or consultants, but also environmental NGOs and local governments will be developed and improved. 5 years after we launched the Nature-based solutions concept for EU Research and Innovation, we are more aware than ever how much we need NBS to tackle the interconnected societal challenges and we need to take the necessary steps to make sure the market is ready for them.</p>	Connecting Nature Enterprise Summit	Public sector organisation	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - carbon market - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal
<p>Is the UN standard on ecosystem accounting a first step to valuation? Ecosystem valuation - Micro level - bottom up accounting - first step ahead of natural capital accounting</p>	IUCN World Conservation Congress	-	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation

Bioeconomy overlap with nature-based economy? Need for clarity around intersection between many concepts – bioeconomy, circular economy, nature-positive economy...	IUCN World Conservation Congress	-	- Standards
Quantifying value - restoration shouldn't be valued. Nature shouldn't be considered an asset. How do you put a monetary value on people's health... If you don't value nature, then it is not appreciated and difficult to secure funding/investment in particular from private sector. Nature can be measured by monetary/non-monetary valuation using qualitative as well as quantitative indicators. Please see EU Guidebook on indicators.	IUCN World Conservation Congress	-	- Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - System change
Question: Consider solidarity economy as part of concept?	IUCN World Conservation Congress	-	- Standards
In the Adopt-a-park Nicosia example: Are the companies saving money in the long run or rather profiting in other ways (such as marketing). Are the tax incentives higher than the "fees"?	Climate Alliance International Conference	-	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy
Poznan: Are you also looking to get the companies to fund the "stewardship" phase? Or get them to take responsibility in other ways (e.g. as CSR / team building events)?	Climate Alliance International Conference	-	- Economic opportunities / challenges
The Ecoprofit programme for SME could be helpful to motivate companies?!? It's a coupling of Energy production, biodiversity, reduction of heat islands.	Climate Alliance International Conference	-	- Knowledge gaps / Capacity building
Trees for Life is trying to develop just such a kind of community based carbon project though their East West Wild project - in development	UK Chartered Forestry Association		- Case studies
The definition of Nature based enterprises talks about sustainability but should such a definition include explicit reference to adherence to relevant sectoral standards/certification/ business transparency? The risk is that NBEs use nature as a means of greenwashing or business advancementI should think McDonalds and Tesco would consider themselves "nature-based enterprises" - so I think needs a tighter definition.	UK Chartered Forestry Association	-	- Standards
From this discussion, does the B-Corp standard work for NBEs? You have repeatedly mentioned Net Gain of Biodiversity what definition of biodiversity net gain and how is it determined? Through an independent 3rd party?	UK Chartered Forestry Association	-	- Standards
Suggestions of other sectors where NBS and NBE's starting to emerge — what about education and really years learning with Forest Schools? Many forest schools in UK are run by private nursery and preschool providers....The Accreditation of these nature based solutions within the forestry industry. Is it under the current guidelines/standards or is there a new category?	UK Chartered Forestry Association	-	- Standards - Economic opportunities / challenges

<p>We need more bottom-up action, aligned with top-down policies, to address the climate change and biodiversity crises. Bottom-up action is already happening - led by people, citizens and civil society at local and city level. These types of actions need to be accelerated. The pandemic has shown us that society and financing can be mobilized into rapid action if the threat is perceived as critical and urgent.</p> <p>"In Peru, our Ministry of Economy and Financing and our Ministry of Environment are working on the direction of climate change. This might be a great opportunity for more businesses based on nature."</p>	<p>Innovate4Cities</p>	<p>Academic/ Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches
<p>Better communication is needed on nature-based solutions (NbS) so that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local communities understand, embrace and are empowered by NbS; - Silos are bridged between environmental and economic policymakers as they realize shared goals - Businesses realize the real threat of depleting natural resources and take action. <p>How can the need for urgent action be better conveyed to these different audiences?</p>	<p>Innovate4Cities</p>	<p>Academic/ Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector
<p>The nature-based economy presents major opportunities for developing countries where nature-based economic activities and primary industry sectors are often more important than in developing countries.</p> <p>Build on local traditions and ancestral knowledge - in many parts of the world people have lived for centuries in harmony with nature - applying approaches to conservation and water management well suited to their local context. These ancient ways of doing things are increasingly being recognised as nature-based solutions. More needs to be done in policy and practice to upscale these local solutions - using co-creation to combine knowledge from local people with that of scientific institutions and public agencies. Technologies such as blockchain present opportunities for local stewardship as well as innovative financing.</p> <p>"Most of Africa is far from reaching an advanced or developed economy status, so defining the development pathway can still be done. Nothing is set in stone, needs to be reversed, or needs to be redone. Instead, we can look at green fields and design a nature-based future"</p>	<p>Innovate4Cities</p>	<p>Academic/ Research institute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
<p>Valuation of nature needs to move away from piecemeal analysis of marginal impacts towards more holistic approaches that take full account of nature's fundamental life-carrying capacity and the complexity of its value-chains. Valuation should be bottom up as well as top down and take into account citizen and community perspectives, enhancing the capacity of decision-makers to confront critical trade-offs in support of sustainability. At the same time, requirements for valuation should not delay the investment in nature that is critically needed. Existing valuation approaches need to be built on and expanded to re-orient public as well as private investment towards nature.</p>	<p>Innovate4Cities</p>	<p>Civil society/NGO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation
<p>SMEs being targeted from so many sides - reduce emissions, incorporate natural capital accounting....now NBS. Sustainability fatigue. Interlink these issues - one approach - explain</p>	<p>Network Nature annual event</p>	<p>-</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Private sector

<p>Accusations of Greenwashing at COP - need to avoid at all costs. Need NbS certification systems - this is what corporate world is looking for. Needs to build on what's been done already IUCN standard One other element being developed by IUCN: Self assessment platform for those applying standard. Corporates need to contribute to this. Peer to peer learning</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Civil society/NGO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Awareness – Private sector - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
<p>Systemic transformation - needs whole society approach A lot of barriers in shift which recognises value of nature NBE, Nature positive economy - concepts recognise need to move to an economy more respectful of nature and boundaries of nature NBEconomy - NBS at the heart of economy</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Public sector organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System change
<p>Example of corporate: 10% of input currently from regenerative agriculture In 3 year aim to have 90% E.g. shea butter - 1 handcream sold every 3 seconds - 20% of handcream shea butter. Working with rural women since 1980's on collection of shea butter in Burkina Faso Aim to create benefits for both women and environment</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Corporate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches
<p>Cement industry - Big CO2 problem -but stress we're not using NBS to offset carbon We're talking about reconciling nature and cities Developed a new (NBS) product - can build trees inside concrete You can build urban forest. Don't have to choose between concrete and city Helps fight heat island effect, Absorbs moisture.. How to create urban forest, green walls, green roofs - not just bringing green into city - many other positive side effects - air quality, rain water mgt, noise pollution etc How to scale up? No incentive today Need to create demand - need to create market Need standard framework - we don't measure nature here (in general) Out of 500 companies, only 7 took scientifically based approach to measuring impact on biodiversity. Support the concept of NBEconomy - integrated P&L - founding member of value based accounting -VBA</p> <p>There are solutions to measure nature - not perfect but they exist. I like concept of incentivising nature - we need the equivalent of CO2 pricing for nature. I would sell a lot of product if there was market demand. Surprised no incentives? What kind of role can regulation play? Waiting too long if waiting for CO2 equivalent. What kind of incentives can we have in the short term.</p> <p>We're not waiting - we've developed a product and put it on the market. We've training our sales</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Corporate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Private sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector

<p>team. We go to C40 Cities... Today we don't see the demand happening. People think of trees and think of parks in city (need to expand thinking to consider GI). Mega trend people moving to cities. Can't build cities without looking at green walls etc. Legislation is not there to drive market demand. In the meantime we talk to decision makers in the city.</p> <p>80% of our R&D going to sustainable solutions. We can't sell our product if no-one wants to buy it.</p> <p>Gamechanger - nature-based economy. I would love to be evaluated on Integrated P&L (shows how much positive and negative value they create for society) rather than P&L.</p>			
<p>Aim is to be net positive for nature by 2030 Need to be able to measure - we don't have equivalent to CO2 for biodiversity - need baseline to know what issues to tackle. Corporate engaged in science for nature. Trying to make science based targets. Making biodiversity footprint of full value chain- look at all pressures on biodiversity - come up with biodiversity score. Work a lot with R&D. Need to base decisions on science. Learning as we go along. Can't wait.</p> <p>Global biodiversity score - were you surprised with results? Haven't got them yet - learning a lot from process Hope to see clear connection between climate and biodiversity. For energy company crucial to link the two. Developing model to ensure hydropower included</p> <p>Examples of how they're supporting biodiversity: Applying technical solutions for offshore winds - bubble curtains to curtail underwater noise - Actively working with nature-based design to secure artificial reefs around pylons - creating cod hotels etc Main challenges? Lack of speed - not moving fast enough Energy transition crucial to protect biodiversity. Need to get better at taking a holistic view - when we do renewable projects - we need to take into account global and local perspectives - we can look at populations instead of individuals and gather different stakeholders. Accepting that huge opportunity and potential in applying new technology - drones, face recognition - need to share knowledge - what measures are most effective.</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Corporate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
<p>Example of NBS: Use bacteria to clean water Act for Nature - international pledge - tool to help us monitor our transformation</p> <p>Example of NBS for water activity:</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Corporate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy

<p>Proposing to build mangrove instead of building dyke in Martinique - better for biodiversity Need to define clearly NBS, put NBS in public tender, have public bodies requesting NBS, putting more weight in tender responses on solutions that have NBS Tertiary fund for water - develop wetland - instead of chemical/mechanical process - to process water - developing on large scale in China. 35 hectares of wetland - cleaning water as part of tertiary treatment. There are solutions - we need to put them in front of our customers. Need to work all together - corporates on panel are in supply chain with each other - we all share the same vision - we have long expertise in water Global awareness of citizens will put pressure on public bodies - will put pressure on B2C man Need regulation, need laws.</p> <p>Waste issue - what are you doing to fight biodiversity collapse? Solving a historic problem e.g. Qatar - birds and fish come back quickly. Once public body has decided to solve an issue, we have the solutions and the biodiversity comes back quickly. Circular economy and biodiversity are closely linked</p> <p>What could be your role in upcycling minerals? Battery - first time EC made obligation of recycling measures - Suez fighting for years for obligation to reuse plastic - using new polymer was cheaper -than recycling need obligation to recycle. Many technical challenges - need RTD partners</p>			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Private sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector sector - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration - Case studies
<p>Nature 2050 is based on the voluntary commitment of economic actors. Thanks to companies' engagement, we support concrete actions carried out by local actors such as NGOs, local authorities, businesses, farmers... All 50 projects carried out will be monitored up to 2050.</p> <p>5 innovations Programme: Nature 2050 launched in 2016 Link btw biodiversity and climate change Use NBS for 5 goals Restoration of wetlands Promote farming and forestry transition - agro forestry Create ecological continuity in France Promote biodiversity in cities (quite new in 2016) Preservation of coastal ecosystem Most important for panel - based on voluntary commitment of company. Company can directly give contribution to CDC - Other important innovation - based on scientific involvement - in governance we have 2 well known french scientists - all projects monitored on ground. Till 2050 - monitor indicators in field related to carbon and biodiversity</p>	<p>European Business and Nature Summit</p>	<p>Funding organisation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges

<p>What sectors are most interested? We work with agro-forestry (one of most important section) 50 projects - forests, vineyards (a lot of problems with dead trees in south of france) Waterlands, wetlands</p> <p>First phase was an experiment Now massive ambition to upscale</p>			
<p>How would you respond on the argument that in order to meet the carbon neutrality commitment of EU by 2050 we rather need to end carbon fuels (including primary woody biomass)? This is also positive to biodiversity</p>	European Business and Nature Summit	-	- System change
<p>Just to mention as confirmed by the recently released Extractive Sector Code of Conduct, even active quarries can be positive for biodiversity through temporary habitats, and that it is not just in the restoration phase. https://www.birdlife.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Code-of-conduct_With-signatures_Digital-low-res.pdf</p>	European Business and Nature Summit		- Awareness – Private sector
<p>Immediate actions to stimulate supply: - Standards the most helpful. Lots of standards in the tourism sector, no harmonisation between the many different bodies and industry standards - Incentives to increase business support programmes - that really helps NBEs like Helix - Awareness of potential needs to grow and credibility of practitioners - joint ethics and standards/ Credibility. - Training A mix of recommendations, not one more important than the other. Incentives can help in the first place but they need to work and be interesting for investors and need to be sustainable.</p>	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Standards - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy
<p>- Cultural aspects of NB economy? Not included - community engagement: Social enterprises, and NGO's community engagement can support NBE's and NBS.</p>	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Economic opportunities / challenges
<p>- Holistic approach is needed. Media dissemination is needed for the N-B economy → building awareness - Nature as medicine - being acknowledged in the health sector - We're very much in a bubble - people still don't know about NBS (in green buildings it is mainly still about aesthetics)</p>	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Awareness – Citizens / Third sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
<p>Public procurement training for local authorities, breaking down silos</p>	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public procurement
<p>What is the return on investment of NBS? Getting the numbers behind the investment is important</p>	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Financial services e.g. natural capital accounting

- Standards - energy is rated, NBS are not. Are they nature-positive? - Not much data on NBS and their impact	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Standards - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation
Forest based care & urban forestry - lack of awareness on opportunities, not necessarily on the benefits. How to access opportunities? Trainings on exploring new markets /opportunities. ERASMUS= - training and capacity building analysis	CNEP Ambassador Feedback Session	Nature-based enterprise	- Economic opportunities / challenges

3.4.2 Feedback from TNOC Roundtable

The Nature Of Cities (TNOC) is a global platform on greening cities. As part of the consultation process, we organised a virtual roundtable on ‘How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy globally?’ where we invited the following experts and practitioners from all over the world to respond. Table 3 shows an overview of the authors, their city, country, and how their contributions were coded.

For an overview of the responses of all authors, see [Appendix A](#).

Table 3 List of contributing authors to the TNOC Roundtable, and an overview of how their contributions were coded

Authors	City, Country	Category (first round)
John Bell & Tiago Freitas	Brussels, Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration - System change
Guilherme Castagna	São Paulo, Brazil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector
Emre Eren & Rupesh Madlani	London, United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Financial services e.g. natural capital accounting - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Economic opportunities / challenges - Financial institutions - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Case studies
Susanne Formanek	Vienna, Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Financial institutions - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
Rhoda Gwayinga & Isaac Mugumbule	Kampala, Uganda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Public sector
Simon Gresset	Freiburg, Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Case studies
Eduardo Guerrero	Bogotá, Colombia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Location - economic situation - capacity to invest - Location - natural environment - Economic opportunities / challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches - System change

		- Case studies
Mamuka Gvilava	Tbilisi, Georgia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Economic opportunities / challenges - Case studies - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Case studies
Cecilia Herzog	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building - Financial institutions - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - System change
Antonia Lorenzo	Málaga, Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - carbon market - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public procurement - Economic opportunities / challenges - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration
David Maddox	New York, United States of America	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Awareness – Private sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - System change - Case studies
Taícia H. N. Marques	Lima, Peru	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration - Knowledge gaps / Capacity building

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Ana Mitić-Radulović	Belgrade, Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Private sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - System change
Hans Müller	Kornwestheim, Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Financial services e.g. natural capital accounting - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Awareness – Public sector - Awareness – Citizens / Third sector - Economic opportunities / challenges
David Simon	London, United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy - Economic opportunities / challenges
Audrey Timm	Chilton, United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach
Ellie Tonks	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Public sector - System change
Naomi Tsur	Jerusalem, Israel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring/ measurement/ - valuation - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach - Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration - Awareness – Public sector - Economic opportunities / challenges - Location - economic situation - capacity to invest
Domenico Vito	Milan, Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic opportunities / challenges - Co-creation / Participatory approaches - Case studies

3.5 Categories of feedback

As described in the methodology for analysis ([Section 2.2](#)), all the feedback in the consultation process was analysed using a bottom up, grounded theory approach. In Table 3 below the results of the coding is shown – from the first round with 22 categories to the second and final round with 8 categories (of which one has 4 subcategories) – and where these are addressed in the EC Expert Publication *The vital role of Nature-Based Solutions in the Nature Positive Economy*.

Table 3 Results of the coding of the consultation responses and where these are addressed in the Expert Publication

First level categories	No. of responses	Final categories	No. of responses	Addressed in Expert Publication in:
Standards	23	Standards	23	Section 5.1
Monitoring/ measurement/ valuation	29	Measurement & Valuation	29	Section 5.2
Financial services e.g., natural capital accounting	4			
Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - economic policy	40	Public policy	49	Section 5.3
Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Carbon market	3			
Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Regulation / legal	29			
Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Planning: holistic approach	20			
Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - cross policy collaboration	28			
Public policy: economic/legal policies instruments - Public procurement	6			

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Knowledge gaps / Capacity building	14	Capacity building & Awareness raising among: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial institutions • Public sector • Private sector • Citizens / Third sector sector 	81	Section 5.4
Financial institutions	8			
Awareness - PUBLIC SECTOR	26			
Awareness - PRIVATE SECTOR	29			
Awareness - Citizens / Third sector	19			
Economic opportunities / challenges	61	Economic opportunities	71	Section 5.5
System change	27			
Location - economic situation - capacity to invest	5	International Perspective - Economic Context	5	Section 4.2
Location - natural environment influences potential for health & wellbeing tourism	20	International Perspective - Natural Environment	20	Section 4.1
Location - culture - citizen willingness to engage and invest	3	International Perspective – Cultural Context	37	Section 4.3
Co-creation / Participatory approaches	13			Section 4.3
Collaboration networks, public-private collaboration	21			Section 4.3
Case studies	14	-	-	Section 5

Acknowledgements

List of H2020 project members of Nature-Based Economy Working Group:

Horizon 2020 [Connecting Nature](#) is a consortium of 30 partners within 16 European countries, and hubs in Brazil, China, Korea & The Caucasus (Georgia and Armenia). We are co-working with local authorities, communities, industry partners, NGOs and academics who are investing in large scale implementation of nature-based projects in urban settings. Grant Agreement number: 730222.

Horizon 2020 [URBINAT](#) focuses on the regeneration and integration of deprived social housing urban developments through an innovative and inclusive catalogue of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), ensuring sustainability and mobilising driving forces for social cohesion. Grant Agreement number: 776783.

Horizon 2020 [UrbanGreenUp](#) aims at developing, applying and validating a methodology for Renaturing Urban Plans to mitigate the effects of climate change, improve air quality and water management and increase the sustainability of cities through innovative nature-based solutions. Grant Agreement number: 730426.

Horizon 2020 [REGREEN](#) promotes urban liveability, through fostering nature-based solutions in Europe and China using evidence-based tools and improved urban governance accelerating the transition towards equitable, green and healthy cities. Grant Agreement number: 821016.

Horizon 2020 [Clearing House](#) uses trees as a means to improve urban living in both Europe and China. Together with 10 cities and urban regions, the project partners will develop an online application, a global benchmark tool, and guidelines that can aid in the design, governance and management of urban forests. Grant Agreement number: 821242.

Horizon 2020 [Network Nature](#) is a resource for the nature-based solutions community, creating opportunities for local, regional and international cooperation to maximise the impact and spread of nature-based solutions. Grant Agreement number: 887396.

Horizon 2020 [Future Mares](#) examines the relations between climate change, marine biodiversity and ecosystem services. Our activities are designed around three Nature-based Solutions (NBS): Effective Restoration, Effective Conservation, and Sustainable Harvesting of Marine Resources. Grant Agreement number: 869300.

Horizon 2020 [MERCES](#) is focused on the restoration of different degraded marine habitats, with the aim of: 1) assessing the potential of different technologies and approaches; 2) quantifying the returns in terms of ecosystems services and their socio-economic impacts; 3) defining the legal-policy and governance frameworks needed to optimize the effectiveness of the different restoration approaches. Grant Agreement number: 689518.

Horizon 2020 [NAIAD](#) aims to operationalise the insurance value of ecosystems for water-related risk mitigation, by developing and testing concepts, tools and applications on 9 demo sites across Europe, under the common concept of Nature Based Solutions (NBS). Grant Agreement number: 730497.

Horizon 2020 [WeValueNature](#) is supporting businesses and the natural capital community to make valuing nature the new normal for businesses across Europe. Grant Agreement number: 821303.

Horizon 2020 [CleverCities](#) uses nature-based solutions to address urban challenges and promote social inclusion in cities across Europe, South America and China. Grant Agreement number: 776604.

Horizon 2020 [Naturvation](#) sought to develop our understanding of what nature-based solutions can achieve in cities, examine how innovation can be fostered in this domain, and contribute to realising the potential of nature-based solutions for responding to urban sustainability challenges by working with communities and stakeholders. Grant Agreement: 730243

[GoGreenRoutes](#) is sowing the seeds for increased nature-connectedness across Europe, Latin America and China. Its multidisciplinary consortium is pairing participatory approaches and citizen science with Big Data analyses and digital innovation.

The [PHUSICOS](#) project will demonstrate how nature-based solutions provide robust, sustainable and cost-effective measures for reducing the risk of extreme weather events in rural mountain landscapes.

JUSTNature

Launched in September 2021 [JUSTNature](#) project will turn to nature-based solutions to ensure a just transition to low carbon cities. Considering the right of all citizens to ecological space, the project will co-design new systems which conserve natural ecosystem values and functions and will ultimately provide numerous benefits to people.

Appendix A: TNOC Roundtable

How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy?

About the Writer:
[Siobhán McQuaid](#)

Siobhan is the Associate Director of Innovation at the Centre for Social Innovation in Trinity College Dublin where she heads up research and innovation activities under the themes of sustainability and resilience.

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Introduction

Nature-based solutions provide an overarching framework embracing concepts and methodologies such as biodiversity net-gain, ecosystem-based adaptation, mitigation, environmental disaster risk reduction, green infrastructure and natural climate solutions to name a few. While much focus to date has been on the environmental or social benefits of nature-based solutions, less attention has been paid to their economic potential and their role in contributing towards more sustainable and just societies.

Indeed, modern economies are not generally build around nature and nature-based solutions — other than extracting from nature. The dire predictions of our climate changed future, now in many way already our present, tell us that this must change. Business as usual is not a prescription for human survival.

So, we ask:

— How do you see nature-based solutions contributing to the sustainable economy of the future?

— How do we go from nature-based solutions to a nature-based economy — where we work in harmony with nature — planning, growing, harnessing, harvesting and/or restoring natural resources in a sustainable way?

— What type of new jobs, new innovations, new enterprises might emerge from a nature-based economy and what are the challenges to uptake of such a concept globally?

These are some of the questions we asked respondents to consider as part of this TNOC virtual roundtable which forms part of a wider consultation on a new White Paper on the Nature-Based Economy.

Is this a discussion simply about assigning monetary value to nature? No, although in a monetized world this is part of the discussion. It is also about creating broad and inclusive discussions about nature and its benefits across the sectors of business, planning, engineering, science, conservation, and community. It is about recognizing the values of nature (in many dimensions) and firmly integrating these values in our economies.

We invite you to respond to the perspectives below or to read more and have your say: visit <https://networknature.eu/consultation-draft-nature-based-economy-white-paper>

About the Writer:
[Daniela Rizzi](#)

Architect/urban planner (Faculty of Architecture & Urbanism of the University of Sao Paulo). Holds a doctoral degree in landscape architecture and planning (Technical University of Munich). Since 2018, Senior Officer on Nature Based Solutions and Biodiversity (CLEI Europe).

Susanne Formanek

About the Writer:
Susanne Formanek

Susanne Formanek is managing director of the innovation laboratory GRÜNSTATTGRAU, initiator of many projects in the green building sector and since 2017 president of IBO, the Austrian Institute for Building Biology and Ecology. This is an independent, non-profit, scientific association that researches the interactions between humans, buildings and the environment. She graduated from the University of Natural Resources and Applied Life Sciences in Vienna in the field of forestry and timber management.

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The environmental and social benefits of NBS are already being recognised as effective measures to combat climate change in the urban regions, whereas the actual value in terms of jobs, innovations, and the economic contribution is not so well known, even by the industry itself.

Based on our [GREENMARKETREPORT](#)

we know today that 38% of the surveyed

companies were founded in the past 10 years. If every other newly constructed building is fitted with a green roof we would generate 33.000 new green jobs in Austria. This means: for every 8,000 m² of additional green roof area, 10 new jobs are created.

Working in harmony with nature means to overcome lack of understanding that maintenance is essential, and that the costs of maintenance need to be budgeted for.

Market potential

The direct value chain of greening buildings just in Austria includes 550 companies and 1200 jobs, whilst the sector is quiet young and has great potential to grow. The branch demands productive interdisciplinary cooperation within the market and between other branches. Therefore the greening buildings and NBS sector provides value for other sectors as well as innovations such as the sectors of construction, circular economy, additive manufacturing, digitalisation etc.

Currently, mainly small and medium-sized companies are active in this country along the entire value chain, from technology development and planning to the manufacture of components, execution and maintenance. The industry is also characterized by a high degree of innovation "made in Austria": The targeted combination of green roofs with other technologies, such as PV, further enhances their impact. These include, for example, solar green roofs in which the cooling effect of the plants boosts the performance of photovoltaics, or the use and purification of gray and service water on roofs.

IMG, AUSTRIAN GREENMARKETREPORT [Wertschöpfungskette AGMR.pdf](#)

Value enhancement

Traditional grey buildings are exposed to all kinds of weather conditions without any protection and need to be renovated from time to time. Greening buildings in comparison acts as a protection shield against weathering and reduces renovation and maintenance costs. Green and living walls and green roofs provide a natural sun screen and insulation. This saves on air conditioning and less energy is used. Green roofs are low-cost in maintenance and long-lasting. Compared to traditional flat roofs, the service life of the roof sealing of a green roof is extended by at least 10 years.

Green infrastructure in and around properties increases the value of the property and the neighbourhood by an average of 4-8%. Improved living conditions lead to higher satisfaction of the inhabitants are convincing reasons to inhabit and stay in greener quarters. Environmental improvements such as better air quality and lower temperatures lead to a healthier population. This increases life expectancy of people but also minimizes sick days leading to reduced costs for sick leave for companies.

From nature-based solutions to a nature-based economy

Working in harmony with nature means to overcome lack of understanding that maintenance is essential, and that the costs of maintenance need to be budgeted for. Our funding program "City of tomorrow" promotes demonstration buildings, and monitoring always playing an important role. Thus, growth performance, vitality of the plant and nature and care and Maintenance can be compared with each other and has a consistency. We are raising awareness by realizing these best practice projects.

The multiple benefits of this nature-based asset can be realised, when a long-term strategy is existing. High quality execution of green infrastructure is also very important. For this reason we have developed standards and new qualification program in Austria, which include maintenance concepts in which we compare the overall costs to the expected benefits and advantages.

Our Biodiversity Strategy Austria 2020+ aims to conserve biodiversity in Austria, to stem the loss of species, genetic diversity and habitats and to minimize the causes of threats. The Biodiversity Strategy Austria 2020+ defines goals and measures for the conservation of biodiversity in Austria. These are based on the international objectives set out in the Convention on Biological Diversity and on those of the European Union.

And we are faced by growing ecomplexity in construction — now also including the interfaces to Building Information Modelling. Our programme “Klima-aktiv building and renovation” implies energy efficiency, ecological quality, comfort and execution quality. Finally our innovation lab GRÜNSTATTGRAU is an instrument of the ministry and funded within City of Tomorrow, and owned by the association of green roofs and green walls in Austria. This is the holistic competence center in Austria for greening buildings focuses especially on the comprehensive benefits of green roofs, living walls and indoor greening. Green infrastructure on buildings provides a broad range of environmental and social benefits and impacts on the building itself, which have great economic value and lead to a sustainable economy.

Green finance

In recent years, the term “green finance” has replaced the term “environmental finance” and defines a spectrum of financial approaches and instruments for environmental and climate protection, for adapting to climate change and for compensation environmental and climate damage. In terms of greening innovations, this approach is important because greening buildings not only benefits the owners, the direct users, but also the surrounding urban landscape and neighbourhood. Therefore, a different financial approach or perspective is needed for climate change measures such as greening buildings. Our program Green Finance 2021 by the “Klima und Energiefond” supports companies and municipalities/cities in carrying out a profitability calculation for planned projects. Innovative solutions and technologies from Austria thus quickly find their way into the domestic and often also international market.

Further information: [eia_03_18_englisch_v03k.pdf](#)
[bmk_InStBegr_Folder_nur-de \(nachhaltigwirtschaften.at\)](#)

About the Writer:

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Taícia H. N. Marques

How do we go from nature-based solutions to a nature-based economy?

This is maybe one of the trickiest questions we must answer, and I am sure there is not only one fine response.

Climate change is already a motor of change, or at least, a motivator of transnational discussions and pacts of changing since quite some time now.

Nevertheless, I have the impression the pandemics of Covid-19, recently reinforced by the last IPCC publication,

made us, or at least some of us, more connected and aware of the urgency

with which we must act. Somehow it shows up a possibility to “re-start” on a much more natural way. On the other hand, the financing of NbS actions to face Climate Change during the recovering from the pandemics is still low. That was/is the moment Nature-based Solutions started to pump up on diverse publications and began gaining more attention in South America, including Peru. This umbrella concept, proposed to put under a common term a bunch of already known techniques and ecosystem approaches, opens new possibilities to different experts and sectors, who normally work focused on one issue, to cooperate and recommend integral solutions for complex problems.

Peru is one of the most biodiverse countries in the world, what makes it one of the most vulnerable areas regarding climate change impacts. Besides that, it faces political and socioeconomical challenges that increases environmental disasters risks and its consequences. During the past decade the country has been closely involved on global and regional pacts for climate, assuming it has an important role to play. Environmental policies in the country are novelty once the Ministry of Environment was only created in 2008 focused on nature conservancy. Nature and economy had traditionally taken different paths, as well as social inclusion, but a possible shift of the business-as-usual model is being recently proposed here.

Currently the country defined two ways towards the sustainability and resilience. The National Policy of Competitivity and Productivity, approved in 2018 by the Ministry of Economics and Finance, incorporates strategies of circular economy to achieve sustainability. It is being complemented by specific roadmaps designed by the Ministry of Environment (MINAM), to guide each one of the most representative economic sectors of the country (industry, agriculture, fishing, and aquaculture), on closing its looping. In parallel, also very fresh, policies and regulations focused on Climate Change mitigation and adaptation are being launched by MINAM. From that, 154 National Determined Contributions are planned, among them Ecosystem based Adaptation (EbA), Natural Infrastructure (IN) actions and different approaches to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions to target 2050 neutrality. Together the two groups of policies settle the bases for Nature-based Solutions in the country and open precedents for a Nature-based economy to be developed. Even though this terminology is very new here, the NbS is already cited on official documents referencing the planned NDC.

Due to the freshness of those policies, together with the institutional debility that affects the country and the commitment it demands to re-think the current economic model, its effectiveness is still unknown. However, it can be a great possibility to impulse Nature-based Solutions and Nature-based Economy together in Peru. What can be current observed is that local EbA and IN interventions have succeed on empowering communities to work with nature to benefit themselves by improving small economies in rural areas, while conserving, restoring, or creating new ecosystems. Yet, the design of business models to support and scale up NbS in Peru is challenging once it encompasses a range of actors and sectors that usually are not used to collaborating.

The design of business models to support and scale up NbS in Peru is challenging once it encompasses a range of actors and sectors that usually are not used to collaborating. To move towards Nature-based Economy there is a need to bring those different actors to the same page of comprehension regarding Nature-based Solutions.

Urban areas also represent a gap of action that should be taken. To move towards Nature-based Economy there is a need to bring those different actors to the same page of comprehension regarding Nature-based Solutions potential and application on different areas of the territory.

About the Writer:
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Ellie Tonks brings expertise in designing and delivering impact orientated climate innovation projects. As Programme Lead of EIT Climate-KIC's Resilient Regions programme Ellie has worked with four European regions over the past 2 years, to design portfolios of climate-resilient adaptation innovations. Ellie has an MSc in Ecological Economics from The University of Edinburgh and a BSc in Ecology and Conservation from St Andrews University.

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Ellie Tonks

As an ecological economist the notion of a nature-based economy should come easily to me. However, it still sits oddly in my stomach. It sends me back to the conversations I would have with peers in ecology and conversation over my decision to study ecological economics. To discussions on their hesitation, resistance and worries towards concepts like “natural capital”, “green growth” or “ecosystem services”. The challenge with these concepts and narratives is the dichotomy between their sub-parts.

When considering a response to the question of “How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy?” I am again confronted by the contract between what I associate as nature-based and as an economy. Therefore, I will try to address my discomfort head-on by setting out a vision for a nature-based economy, followed by why we must look past only the economic potential of NBS.

My vision for a (global) nature-based economy, is an economic system that is embedded within our social system, which is in turn is embedded within our ecological system. In other words, a nature-based economy is operating within our planetary boundaries, working mutually towards net-zero and resilience efforts. It is an economy in which the production and consumption of nature-based goods and services are used to meet the needs of the communities they serve, whilst regenerating and building resilience in the (eco)systems they rely on. For example, timber sustainably harvested from local mixed-species forest is used to substitute carbon intensive materials like cement or steel in construction efforts; meeting housing needs, whilst supporting local labour markets via the new jobs needed to process and build with wood. This example, however, sets out the fragility of the nature-based economy as it is an economy that must be deliberate and purposeful. The forests, for example, if not planted and managed to regenerate soils, promote biodiversity, and build resilience to future climate scenarios, can further lock-in vulnerabilities to our systems. As a result, the increased use of timber in construction, though it would realise quantifiable carbon benefits via carbon storage in wood-based produces in addition to providing new local economic opportunities, could jeopardise the ecological system in which it lives. Nature-based economies must therefore be designed deliberately.

The NBS that are the constitute elements of our nature-based economy can help realise whole system scale impacts, and not just economic benefits. Considering these systems scale benefits can support new business models and financing schemes, whilst creating the enabling conditions to grow new nature-based businesses and start-ups. For example, vacant and derelict land in cities represents a very physical opportunity for the nature-based economy to thrive within urban areas, however, the redevelopment of this land falls short in the development case when landowners hold off in the hope that land value will increase in the future. In other words, at present our economy is favouring a

At present, our economy does not favour a nature-based development agenda. But if a holistic case was built around the climate change adaptation and/or community health co-benefits, we could start to piece together a more compelling nature-based development case.

different development agenda. Whereas, if a holistic case was built around the climate change adaptation (e.g. water retention or urban cooling benefits) and/or community health (e.g. improved mental health and wellbeing or pollution reduction) co-benefits we could start to piece together a more compelling development case. This development case will never represent the full systems benefits of NBS (e.g. cultural, heritage or ecological values), however, it will support the growth of our nature-based economy, and in turn help the realisation of these multifaceted benefits.

In summary, we need to be purposeful when designing both the NBS that constitute our future nature-based economies, and the future nature-based economy itself. Both need to be net-zero, resilience building, and regenerative in their design.

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Guilherme Neves Castagna is a civil engineer, ecological designer, and integrated water management specialist based in São Paulo, Brazil. Guilherme is also a founding partner at Fluxus Design Ecológico, a multi-awarded engineering and ecological design firm that designs integrated water management infrastructure for clients ranging from traditional and vulnerable communities to industries, commercial development projects and municipalities. Fluxus advocates for water literacy, offering courses and workshops, and produce educational materials in multiple media for both general and technical public, strengthening a new culture of mutually beneficial relationship with water.

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Guilherme Neves Castagna

No longer regarded as experiments, NBS are being implemented across the world in challenging situations while providing a multitude of beneficial functions, whether for the built, or the natural environment. As it gains momentum, and wide scale recognition of its benefits, successful NBS implementation offer tangible results that can be measured, scrutinized, and actually sensed by those able to accompany its impact. The fresh air and pleasant microclimate produced by a newly planted forest in the heart of a densely occupied city is easily perceived (and welcomed) by anyone that has had the experience of walking through the same place under the scorching sun; in that sense, the actual benefits felt by one's senses are enough to perceive its positive impact.

The consequences of such perceptions are long and far reaching. Bringing its positive impact to our senses help changing one's perspective to a very practical level, where solutions deemed as complicate and out-of-reach appear somewhat closer to us, and no longer dependent upon the sole discretion of high-ranked public managers. Lay people are able to understand that small-scale, decentralized solutions can, and do play an important role in improving lives, and start demanding like-minded solutions in other areas. It is just natural then that one starts to ask, what implications derive from our very daily choices on transport, banking, health-care, and many other components of our economy, and how can these choices support the creation of similar benefits in their daily operations? Yes, businesses need to be part of the solution!

In larger scale projects, whether public or private, direct experience is not always accessible and so further measurements are necessary. The use of consolidated metrics, like ROI, however, tend to be quite limited and demand a new approach — one that encompasses benefits that go beyond limited financial metrics and delve into human and natural capital, whose valuation, although complex, allows for checking on real progress. Increased biodiversity then, being the very foundation of NBS, can help establishing relevant indexes that support the growth of real nature-based economy. After all, no economy is possible without a sound natural capital in place.

Increased biodiversity, being the very foundation of NBS, can help establishing relevant indexes that support the growth of real nature-based economy. After all, no economy is possible without a sound natural capital in place.

About the Writer:

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Antonia Lorenzo is Bachelor of Agricultural Chemistry and specialist in Environmental Engineering and Technology, and currently doing her PhD in Economic evaluation of the use of reclaimed water in agriculture at the University of Córdoba, Spain. Antonia is founder, CEO and R&D director at BIOAZUL. She has worked for 20 years in the management and implementation of more than 60 national and international projects, mainly related to blue infrastructures for the sustainable water management - treatment, water reuse, ecological sanitation, nature-based solutions – as well as circular economy and resources sustainability.

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Antonia Lorenzo

I believe the role of nature-based enterprises is essential in the transition towards a nature-based economy.

Stimulating and supporting the growth of these enterprises specialised in NBS will contribute to accelerate the development of more sustainable economic systems. In this sense, it is important to establish incubators and mentoring programmes to entrepreneurs, including capacity building activities oriented to NBS, not only technical but also training in business and finance mobilisation to ensure success and business continuity. At the same time, there is a large number of small and medium enterprises already established, with wide experience, that have the capacity to adapt their technologies, services and business lines and shift them towards a NBS-oriented market. Supporting and guiding existing companies and organisations in this adaptation process, as change agents, will add to the transition to a greener economy.

In fact, the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF), together with the International Labour Organization (ILO)^[1], have recognised the importance of protecting and preserving natural systems in supporting employment, with currently around 1.2 billion jobs in sectors such as farming, fisheries, forestry and tourism, highly dependent on the effective management and sustainability of ecosystems. They conclude that half of the world's Gross Domestic Product is, to a greater or lesser degree, dependent on nature.

This analysis is also supported by the World Economic Forum^[2], that has identified a wide range of professions of the future emerging from a greener economy and provides a list of jobs which are to some extent related to NBS, such as sustainability specialists, water resource specialists, or water/wastewater engineers. These professions will require distinctive skills and additional learning, for instance in geographic information systems (GIS), global environmental management and water resources management and policy.

However, even though there is a large and increasing number of nature-based enterprises ready to deliver NBS, we still need to understand each other better (public – private collaboration) and work together more. In collaborating with the public sector, there are difficulties in terms of procurement of NBS and the problem of silo-thinking. NBS are still complex to implement, and policies need to be harmonized to enable implementation. Public procurement can be a powerful driver for NBS and thus nature-based enterprises, but it is rather challenging to find opportunities and see how NBS are included.

Notes:

¹ Lieuw-Kie-Song, M., & Perez-Cirera, V. (2020). [Nature hires: how nature-based solutions can power a green jobs recovery](#). World Wide Fund For Nature (formerly World Wildlife Fund), Gland, Switzerland and International Labour Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.

² Ratcheva, V., Leopold, T. A., & Zahidi, S. (2020). [Jobs of tomorrow: mapping opportunity in the new economy](#). In World Economic Forum, Geneva, Switzerland.

Even though there is a large and increasing number of nature-based enterprises ready to deliver NBS, we still need to understand each other better (public – private collaboration) and work together more, especially in procurement.

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Isaac Luwaga Mugumbule is the Head of Landscaping at the Kampala Capital City Authority. He holds a degree in Architecture with specialized training in green infrastructure management and urban design and has 12 years experience in the built environment and urban landscape. He led Kampala's first urban forestry audit and development of an urban green infrastructure ordinance.

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Isaac Mugumbule and Rhoda Gwayinga

The concept of Nature-based economy (NbE) is new to the City of Kampala and to most cities across the globe. In the past, we have had a lot of dialogue around Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and Impacts of Climate change on a country's economy but never on the same platform. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), it defines Nature-based Solutions (NbS) as "actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits". This umbrella of NbS creates the opportunity to incorporate other urban actors in the discussion on NbE.

Governments, policy makers, experts and private sector need to collaborate and develop Nature-based economic indicators. These could explore factors like urban forestry cover, air quality, blue infrastructure, population growth, green technology. NbE indicators would then be used as a basis for driving key economic policy decisions as opposed to the norm.

Kampala City is the Capital City of Uganda and is located next to one of Africa's largest natural asset, Lake Victoria, the largest lake in Africa. Another major natural asset in Uganda is the longest river in Africa, River Nile, which also originates from Lake Victoria. Unlike most cities, Kampala has two population figures, that is a night population (residents) of 1.65 million people and day-time population of 4.0 million people (UBOS, 2019). This large disparity in the two population figures shows the urbanization pressures this city faces. However, if the city fails to protect the ecosystem around Lake Victoria, then this will have devastating effects not only on the economies of countries within the Lake Victoria basin but also the countries served by the River Nile all the way up to Egypt in Northern Africa. It should be noted that these two large natural assets have been critical in guiding economic discussions within Africa and have led to the formation of key economic groups, that is the East Africa Community (EAC) which consists of six partner states and the Nile Basin Initiative (NBI) which consists of eleven partner states. More than half the global population now lives in towns and cities.

By the year 2050, UN-Habitat research projects that the figure will rise to two-thirds. According to the Kampala Physical Development Plan (KPDP), it is projected that by 2040, a population of 10 million people will be living in Kampala. In order to mitigate the pressures of urbanization, Kampala Capital City Authority (KCCA) developed a 5-year strategic plan (2020-2025) aimed at addressing the challenges of urbanization in a holistic approach. This strategy incorporated the KPDP, Disaster Risk and Climate Resilience strategy, the Kampala Drainage Masterplan and the Kampala Climate Change Action Plan (KCCAP). According to the Disaster Risk Resilience strategy, an integrated approach has been set out in managing disasters in the city. This includes avoiding creating risks, reducing existing risks, responding more efficiently to disasters and mitigating the effects of climate and building climate resilience. The resilience strategy will inform KCCA's Investment planning and operations for the strategic plan, as well as sectoral plans and Investments. KCCAP aims at mainstreaming climate change response in all city services in order to put the city on a low carbon development path.

NbE essentially looks at how cities will effectively utilize the existing resources in a sustainable way while building resilience and maintaining a balanced ecosystem amidst the threat of climate change. Governments, policy makers, experts and private sector need to collaborate and develop Nature-based economic indicators. These could explore factors like urban forestry cover, air quality, blue infrastructure, population growth, green technology. NbE indicators would then be used as a basis for driving key economic policy decisions as opposed to the norm. All governments need to closely monitor these NbE indicators and any negative change should trigger a warning that will translate to an appropriate response to mitigate the looming crisis.

About the Writer:
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David Simon

Although the term “nature-based solutions” (NBS) has become widely used and recognised only fairly recently, the value of natural areas and biodiversity to human wellbeing and sustainability has long been recognised. Various forms of national park, nature reserve, botanical garden and other protected area have been created around the world for well over a century, while the shift of emphasis from saving individual endangered species to the need to conserve them as part of threatened habitats, ecosystems and ecobiomes began several decades ago.

A — and perhaps the — key value of NBS and the closely related concept of ecosystem services (ESs) lies in their focus on problem solving and the services provided by the environment. ESs go one stage further in seeking to quantify the value of four principal categories of such service (provisioning, regulating, supporting and cultural). While decried by critics as reducing intrinsic values to utilitarian economic value and privileging those services that can be quantified, the inclusion of cultural services and the recognition in the other categories of the value of integrated, multispecies ecosystems is intended to avoid simplistic economisation. Underpinning that perspective is the argument that in this capitalistic and increasingly monetised world, attaching tangible values to ecosystems and the services they perform is the most likely way to conserve them.

While decried by critics as reducing intrinsic values to utilitarian economic value and privileging those services that can be quantified, the inclusion of cultural services and the recognition in the other categories of the value of integrated, multispecies ecosystems is intended to avoid simplistic economisation. In a monetized world, attaching tangible values to ecosystems and the services they perform is the most likely way to conserve them.

The oldest and most-established forms of nature-based economy exist in predominantly rural areas. These include schemes to pay farmers to retain uncultivated areas (known as Set Aside by the European Commission), and conserve biodiverse features such as hedgerows and reedbeds on wetland margins. Such payments recognise the economic value of ‘natural’ and uncultivated areas and their ecosystem services. Rural afforestation schemes are also increasingly moving away from monoculture forestry plantations towards more biodiverse mixed species areas, and sometimes paying owners not to fell native forests in the first place as a precursor to establishing plantations.

Another example is nature-based tourism, a massive growth area in many countries and regions, where nature reserves, national parks and private resorts experience development of activities from skiing to watersports, hiking, survival courses and wildlife safaris. The unsustainability of many large-scale conventional schemes has spawned rapid growth of ‘eco-tourist’ initiatives with lower impacts, greater local integration and employment and hence supposedly greater lasting local economic benefit.

In and around urban areas, high-density nature-based leisure and recreation areas like country parks, lakes and reservoirs and coastal resorts often combine diverse activities that comprise important economic assets, albeit of varying local embeddedness and sustainability. There is important scope to upgrade, enhance and expand these in various ways, including (a) expanding and linking isolated “natural” areas like pocket parks to develop more integrated green-blue infrastructure that has far higher ecological value and opens nature to residents in all areas, especially poorer neighbourhoods which usually fare badly on local green space; and (b) by environmental restoration/(re-)wilding and increasing their use of indigenous vegetation and adapting them for climate change resilience.

Large-scale commercial peri-urban agriculture is an important contributor to urban food supply and security in Cape Town, South Africa. Photo: David Simon

Sustainable urban and peri-urban agriculture at both micro and commercial smallholder scales has substantial development potential in many regions, providing livelihoods to poor and low-income people and contributing to reducing food miles and greater city-regional food supply resilience (see photo above). Replacing exotic vegetation in urban parks, roadside beds and embankments with native/indigenous species that are more climate resilient and have greater urban biodiversity value is an increasingly urgent nature-based economic activity in its own right, not least through commercial scale plant/tree nurseries.

Other forms of urban greening (see photo below) help to reduce the urban heat island effect, make outdoor areas more attractive and hence add value to restaurants, pubs and other facilities, enhance senses of well-being and mental health, hence potentially reducing the cost of mental health and related treatment.

A very biodiverse green wall abutting an outdoor café area at a new cinema in Chiswick, London, England. Photo: David Simon

About the Writer:
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Dr John Bell is the "Healthy Planet" Director in DG Research & Innovation. He is responsible for leading the Research and Innovation transitions on Climate Change within planetary boundaries, Bioeconomy, Food Systems, Environment and Biodiversity, Oceans and Arctic, Circular Economy, Water and Bio-based innovations.

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Tiago Freitas lives in Brussels and is a policy officer at DG Research and Innovation of the European Commission, focusing on biodiversity and Nature-based Solutions. In the past, he has worked at the European Parliament (2004-2010), first as policy advisor and then as research analyst in structural and cohesion policies.

John Bell and Tiago Freitas

Europe's Green Deal Missions is to make peace with nature. Research and Innovation needs a greater level of ambition to set direction for this transition.

Our livelihoods, well-being and our chance to meet the global warming challenge all depend on Nature. Nature provides all sorts of essential services to humanity: clean air and water, food and pollination, it sustains tourism and leisure activities, it contributes to mental and physical health and delivers many other functions.

Nature, in many instances, is also the most effective insurance policy – protecting us from floods, landslides, fires or extreme heat. The tragic natural disasters that have hit Europe and the world this summer have all been a stark reminder of how much we need this protection. Natural capital stocks per capita have declined by nearly 40% between 1992 and 2014 and one million plant and animal species now face extinction. All this while roughly half of the world's GDP is moderately or highly dependent on Nature.

This is a serious threat to our future welfare and calls for the development of an Economy that is more respectful of Nature.

At the centre of this paradigm shift are Nature-based Solutions (NBS). They are increasingly recognised internationally as a fundamental part of action for climate and biodiversity. A UNEP report issued last May states that investments in NBS need to triple by 2030^[1] if the world is to meet its climate change, biodiversity and land restoration targets.

A growing number of businesses is making the case for NBS already, but it is time to move from niche to a broader movement. Hence, while NBS are already being delivered, are visible and credible, we need a greater uptake, including through the supportive policy framework offered by the European Green Deal.

A recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic is another chance to bring back nature to the core of our societies. National Recovery and Resilience Plans, which aim to build a more sustainable and resilient economy across Europe are a once in a life-time opportunity for a nature-based recovery.

The potential for local job creation is tremendous, comprising both highly technical green jobs but also other jobs that are low-skilled, offering a chance to reach those who have been hit hardest by the pandemic.

The potential is huge. However, unlocking full NBS potential will need a massive increase in investment, both public and private and will hinge on a paradigm shift in how our economies are organised and how they value nature and its services. A transformation is needed in our current business model, bringing local actors to the driving seat for changes.

The potential is huge. However, unlocking full NBS potential will need a massive increase in investment, both public and private and will hinge on a paradigm shift in how our economies are organised and how they value nature and its services. A transformation is needed in our current business model, bringing local actors to the driving seat for changes.

We need to move towards:

- An Economy that puts Nature at its heart and acknowledges that biodiversity is absolutely essential to secure long-term sustainable economic growth;
- An Economy that is aligned with Nature and Climate goals, including through incentive structures, fiscal and budgetary policies;
- An Economy with more holistic objectives and measures of progress that look beyond economic growth/GDP

Such an Economy would create opportunities for viable, large-scale NBS across various sectors, while creating a win-win for nature, climate, and the people.

We have mobilised research and innovation to support policy here: 28 projects are underway worth EUR 240 million on demonstrating how to deploy NBS. Additionally, large-scale ecosystem restoration projects on land and at sea from our Horizon 2020 Green Deal call (mobilising EUR 86 million) will start this autumn.

NBS also feature prominently in Horizon Europe's Work programmes for 2021-2022, in the Biodiversity Partnership as well as in Horizon Europe's Missions, notably the one on Adaptation to climate change and Oceans.

In a nutshell – we are not short of ideas. Science is clear on what needs to be done, but it is time to deliver innovation, demonstration of NBS – across policy, business and civil society.

Opportunities are plentiful and it is entirely in our hands to move to a greener, safer and more equitable economy that leaves no one behind, now that the world grapples with unprecedented climate and biodiversity emergencies.

[1] And to quadruple by 2050, Source: [State of Finance for Nature | UNEP – UN Environment Programme](#)

About the Writer:
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Mamuka Gvilava is environmental sustainability expert at GeoGraphic Ltd., based in Tbilisi, Georgia, experienced with cooperative projects in the Caucasus and Black Sea regions. His expertise includes environmental and strategic impact assessments, earth observations, green procurement, and nature-based solutions, latter gained within the European Connecting Nature project, co-founding the NBS UrbanByNature Caucasus hub together with the colleagues from the region.

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Mamuka Gvilava

It is time to promote Nature-Based Development

A paradigm shift is required in development financing. Project appraisals by international (and national) funding institutions (IFIs) currently are based mostly on economic grounds and technical cost-benefit analysis after political funding decisions are made through country strategies etc., while nature, environment and even social factors are considered as second thoughts through so called environmental and social safeguards, such as environmental impact assessments and resettlement frameworks. As for health and safety, it is believed that they can be “controlled”.

In order for the development to become nature-based and contribute into nature-based economy, political and technical decision-making should be substituted by nature-based decision making: whenever the sectoral project is not nature-based as a priority, expect unexpected.

Luckily there is some experimentation by IFIs putting nature and environment at the front-end of the decision-making. A good example of this is the EBRD's Green Cities initiative. There are plenty of examples even in my city of Tbilisi, Georgia, in the Caucasus, demonstrating how beneficial projects developed under the Tbilisi's Green City Action Plan are, and how much damage can be self-inflicted when they are not.

Nature-Based Economic development could indeed be the necessary, not merely sufficient condition for genuinely sustainable development. Any publicly supported project should be providing nature-based solution.

Nature-Based Economic development could indeed be the necessary, not merely sufficient condition for genuinely sustainable development. In a sense, any project publicly supported should be providing nature-based solution.

Not convinced? Then just think how intrusion into bat habitats by transportation schemes and humans settlements resulted in our global pandemic stalemate . Who would think about bats seriously?

About the Writer:
[Hans Müller](#)

Master gardener and managing director. Owner of three agricultural production horticultural businesses and managing partner of Helix Pflanzen GmbH and Helix Pflanzensysteme GmbH. Vertical greening has been part of Hans Müller's entire horticultural career. For about 15 years there has been a clear strategic corporate orientation to harness ecosystem services from vertical vegetation. Hans Müller and the company Helix Pflanzen GmbH have since worked in various national and international research consortia. In 2017, Hans Müller received the Taspo Award in gold as horticultural entrepreneur of the year 2017

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Hans Müller

How can nature-based solutions (NBS) provide the basis for a nature-based economy?

One important key is monetizing the ecosystem services provided by nature. Without doing this, without giving an economic value to NBS there will be no significant and natural development for a nature-based economy.

Why is that?

Economic processes are based on the principle of cost and value of goods and services. Also, the principle of opportunities and risks.

What is the cost of pollution, what is the cost of missing green, missing trees and shrubs in urban areas? It just started to price the Co2 emissions. It is well known, that taxes on cars per year does not match the hidden cost of pollution and health risk on man per year and car. This need to change!

The other perspective: Studies have shown that the timespan patients stay in hospitals is shorter, when their hospital room facing into a lush green space. Patients locking into a Park or green area shortens their stay in hospital and the health system saves money. This money should be made available to the owner of the Park for their maintenance budget.

Politics has to have a close look at that and need to prepare fair rules to enable the development of nature-based economy. To value, the cost of pollution and the value of ecosystem services of NBS need to get visible, and the bill needs to be paid. Then there will be budgets for NBS and also for the transformation towards an NBE

Market-based mechanism will then boost the nature-based economy.

Maybe this sounds too simple for you — you are right — it is not. It is far more complicated, I know. Anyway, the roles to the economic playground needs to be sharpened by politics.

To me there are two levels of developments concerning a nature-based economy

1. The NBE (Nature based Enterprise) Startups focusing on NBS
2. Classic / traditional companies transferring towards an NBE

Both are important and for both I see economic advantages.

To me, there are already many signs towards a nature-based economy: Public demand for NBS is visible and not many companies can provide goods and services at the moment. The public awareness towards the climate crises and lack of biodiversity leads to NBS. Cooperate Financing will get harder without a CSR report including environmental aspects. The Fridays for future generation is highly sensible for the eco aspects, and they are the future employees and CEOs.

Let's get started and monetize Eco System services on a wide scale!

There are two levels of developments concerning a nature-based economy: (1) The NBE (Nature based Enterprise) Startups focusing on NBS; (2) Classic / traditional companies transferring towards an NBE. Both are important and for both I see economic advantages.

About the Writer:
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Naomi Tsur

It has taken many decades for the issue of climate change to gain center stage in the global conversation, and even now that has been achieved, who knows how much longer it will take for the necessary steps to be taken to re-establish the balance between man and nature that is essential for our civilization to survive?

As the conversation develops, so do the misunderstandings that arise in the course of any discussion. Particularly acerbic is the superfluous argument between the teams set on protecting biodiversity (the root problem), and the teams working to achieve the goal of zero emissions. These last are often so focused on their task, that they sometimes seem to forget why they are doing it.

There is no doubt that nature-based solutions contribute to the economy, but that does not necessarily mean that they can provide the basis for a complete economic framework. But nature in and around cities is gradually earning the right to be recognized as a very significant layer of infrastructure, along with water and food (agriculture). This is, effectively, the infrastructure that gives us life.

Meanwhile nature in and around cities, historically viewed as the “leftovers” of urban development, is gradually earning the right to be recognized as a very significant layer of infrastructure, along with water and food (agriculture). This is, effectively, the infrastructure that gives us life.

Parallel to the painfully slow increase in awareness of the simple fact that it is we who need nature and not the reverse, it is now understood that nature itself can provide some of the best means of defense for the other kinds of infrastructure that we hold so dear, such as transport systems, buildings of all kinds, in short our urban fabric.

I have been following the course of urban and peri-urban nature for the last 25 years, and it has been, and continues to be a fascinating journey. In my own city, Jerusalem, I am familiar with the details of every step in the journey, but I see similar processes in many other cities around the world. These are the steps I have followed closely in Jerusalem:

- The discovery of natural areas within cities that have not been built on or developed as neatly sculpted gardens.
- The understanding that these areas have cultural, educational and recreational value for the local urban community.
- The realization that these areas have been guardians of various species, and indeed enabled their survival.
- The appreciation that nature within the city can be part of the broader picture, in that ecological corridors do not end at the city boundary, but in fact run through the city, a reality that needs to be incorporated into urban planning.
- The grasp of the potential contribution of urban nature to mitigation of and adaptation to climate change. For example, we all know the importance of trees in our cities, the contribution of well-managed community gardens to the restoration of damaged habitats and local food-growing is well-known, and many cities have used natural areas to protect their drainage basins from catastrophic flooding.
- More recently, the value of nature-based solutions has gained greater recognition, along with the understanding that such “solutions” can have enormous economic value, especially when it comes to preventing floods, ensuring that run-off from rainwater is safely filtered before flowing back into underground water reserves, or harvesting rainwater for use in drier seasons, in the case of arid climates.

There is no doubt that nature-based solutions contribute to the economy, but that does not necessarily mean that they can provide the basis for a complete economic framework. If I take as an example one of the famous case studies from Jerusalem, the Gazelle Valley Park, I believe it is entirely possible to quantify the economic benefit of the initiative, independent of the clear social and environmental benefits.

- It is a nature park, designed to cater for the herd of gazelles that live there. There are therefore no electric lighting installations, so as not to disturb the gazelles' natural cycle. Result: a lot of money saved.
- It is a nature park, so the gardening required is minimal and low maintenance. Result: a lot of money saved.
- The park is designed as part of the Soreq drainage basin. The lakes in the park are formed from winter rainfall, and supplemented in summer with tertiary treated sewage water. No tap water is used. Result: a lot of money saved.
- The park covers 65 acres, in the heart of the city. There is enormous demand for housing near the park. Result: a lot of money in city coffers from successful urban renewal initiatives.
- The Gazelle Park has become a tourist attraction, apart from having become a global bird lovers' destination. Result: income for the city, when tourists add a day to their schedule to include the park.

These points illustrate the economic significance of one urban nature park in Jerusalem. There are many additional projects, and many more potential ones. I would posit that in Jerusalem, as in almost any other city, nature-based solutions can and should play an integral role in the urban economy, alongside other significant urban sectors.

About the Writer:
[Simon Gresset](#)

Simon Gresset is a Circular Economy Officer at ICLEI Local Government for Sustainability. Involved on various projects at European level, he supports local governments in enabling and promoting more circular systems. He is also keen on reminding how the circular transition can help in meeting their environmental, social and economic goals. Simon has an academic background in political sciences and urban planning and previous experiences in innovation management as well as in environmental policy at local government level.

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Simon Gresset

Before joining ICLEI, I used to work as environmental policy officer for a local authority in France, for a “département” located in the Paris region. The area was densely urbanised, with a poverty rate way above national average, numerous environmental issues and poor access to green spaces. I am definitely not an expert in nature-based solutions but I was somehow involved in the making of an ambitious plan aiming at a twofold increase of the canopy cover locally over the 10 following years.

The plan comprised a lot of different conventional actions, such as tree planting and ecosystem restoration, but also the development of support tools, such as a spatial analysis platform to identify areas where renaturation was the most important (based on a set of both environmental and social indicators) and a tool aiming at selecting the most adapted tree for each development based on context and on ecosystemic services it could provide. It also integrated measures aiming to raise awareness among local communities. This plan wasn't obviously going to substantially boost the local economy or significantly transform the urban environment. Still, since its inception it has been supporting useful research and innovation projects while also directly creating several jobs related to the nature based-economy locally. Over the years, it will positively impact the urban environment, making the air more breathable and less warm in summer, and will strengthen the social fabric, creating bonds between inhabitants through community initiatives such as urban gardening.

A project to expand canopy in Paris would undoubtedly improve the quality of life of locals, and it could in turn create new investment opportunities, spark new interests among communities for the environment and foster new initiatives, constituting some sort of virtuous circle.

Overall this will undoubtedly improve the quality of life of locals, and it could in turn create new investment opportunities, spark new interests among communities for the environment and foster new initiatives, constituting some sort of virtuous circle. This is a small example based on personal experience but I assume that the multiplication and upscaling of such actions at local government level can constitute the basis of a growing nature-based economy with a strong potential for both people and for the environment.

About the Writer:
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Eduardo Guerrero is a biologist with over 20 years of experience in projects and initiatives involving environmental and sustainable development issues in Colombia and other South American countries.

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Eduardo Guerrero

Circular economy as a nature-based solution for green and sustainable cities in a megadiverse country

Circular economy is actually a nature-based solution, in which business and productive activities emulate an ecosystem's efficiency regarding the use of water, raw materials, biomass and energy. So, the main contribution of this concept is the link of economy and nature encouraging an evolution of the conventional economic view about nature as if it were an external factor and an endless spring of resources. In fact, economic and ecological cycles are closely interlinked, so dichotomies that confront economy and environment are more than ever unwise.

Some key challenges (and opportunities) of the urban circular economy for a tropical megadiverse country are: (1) Urban metabolism analysis leads to better decisions; (2) Green entrepreneurship creates a culture of sustainability; (3) Local citizen can drive a circular economy.

Akin to related concepts such as bioeconomy, biotrade, climate economy, green growth, and green business, the circular economy model is generating a new paradigm pointing to a sustainable economy aligned with a global energy transition and biodiversity conservation urgency.

Urban metabolism analysis as a basis to circular economy solutions should be systemic integrating urban biodiversity and ecosystem services. Photo: Eduardo Guerrero

Circular economy in a megadiverse country

In terms of economy-nature synergies, the ecosystemic context and economic emergent dynamics of a country with a high biodiversity such as Colombia offer important opportunities, and challenges related to circular economy implementation.

Cities and metropolitan areas in the Caribbean, Andean, Pacific, Amazon and Orinoquia regions have an enormous space for improvement and the generation of new ventures associated with regional nature advantages.

Circular economy links ecosystem cycles and services, so that the potential of the exceptional Colombian biodiversity is better utilized. And there, clearly, an urban-regional territorial approach is required in which cities are the leveraging nuclei of productive activities and nature conservation, at the same time.

Colombia is a regional leader in terms of public policies promoting circular economy. The National Strategy of Circular Economy was launched in 2019 involving a strong partnership among public and private stakeholders. Moreover, the new stage of the environment policy for cities includes urban circular economy as one of its strategic focuses.

Urban circular economy

Within the global current transition scenario towards a sustainable zero-carbon economy aligned to a halted biodiversity loss, cities are fundamental spaces. Likewise, sustainable cities require a strong development of circular economy schemes, since they are home to a good part of the productive activity and, in addition, the largest population of consumers.

In a city evolving towards sustainability, nature should be an integral part of the urban planning, so that infrastructure, buildings, and mobility corridors are articulated with ecological networks, which are the natural support base for economic production cycles.

Economy and ecology find an opportunity for synergy in urban areas, inspired by the common benefit and pointing to integrated goals of environmental sustainability, economic competitiveness, and social inclusion.

From the perspective of a tropical megadiverse country, some key challenges (and opportunities) of the urban circular economy to consolidate green and sustainable cities are:

Urban metabolism analysis to make better decisions both economic and environmental

To approach the planning of a city in the perspective of the circular economy, one must begin by understanding its metabolism, i.e., the balance between inputs and outputs of water, energy, materials, and biomass. Urban biodiversity and ecosystem services should be an integral part of the analysis.

And we must not forget the social and economic dynamics. Therefore, the analysis of urban metabolism must be systemic, integrating ecological, economic and social flows.

Therefore, it would be advisable to carry out studies and analyses of urban metabolism for each of the country's city-regions, identifying these particularities, comparative advantages and opportunities for entrepreneurship.

Green entrepreneurship articulated with a culture of sustainability, circularity, innovation, and competitiveness

There are multiple opportunities for the development of enterprises based on the bioeconomy with circularity criteria that articulate existing capacities in urban centers with the comparative advantages of the biodiversity of each city-region.

Businesses based on technologies for water reuse, biotechnology, urban agriculture, nature tourism on an urban-regional scale, bio-commerce with an emphasis on local products (with a low carbon footprint), improved production and marketing of natural medicines and nutraceuticals. These and other green business can be integrated into circular economy models with a greater efficiency in the use of resources inspired on ecological cycles.

Local and citizen-driven circular economy

In addition to public policies and private sector commitment regarding circular economy, a key decisive challenge is to achieve a solid appropriation of circular habits by citizens.

At a local and neighborhood scale, strong education, training, and participation initiatives should be supported dealing not only with concepts but mainly with best practices. Rain harvesting, home composting, source separation, reuse of packaging and discarded objects, including their creative transformation into toys, ornaments, costumes, boxes, homemade tools, among others, must be disseminated and expanded.

Circular economy begins at home.

Rainwater harvesting at home is a good example of citizen-driven circular economy. Photo: Eduardo Guerrero

About the Writer:
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Rupesh spent a decade at Lehman Brothers and Barclays in equity research in sustainability and clean technology, ranking first in the Institutional Investor survey. Prior to this, Rupesh worked at PwC in the corporate finance practice. Rupesh has a degree in economics from the London School of Economics, is a chartered accountant and Freeman of the City of London. Rupesh is an expert reviewer in various publications with the World Economic Forum, the OECD, *Princes of Wales*

About the Writer:
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Emre has acquired experience in multiple projects at BwB working on the innovative finance structures required to fund projects, covering a wide list of sustainability linked subjects including energy, biodiversity, debt restructuring, circularity, green infrastructure and retrofit. Emre holds a BSc Hons Accounting and Finance degree from LSE having achieved a First-Class Honours. He is also an entrepreneur having established his own start-up.

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Rupesh Madlani and Emre Eren

Nature based solutions can only provide the framework and foundations of a nature-based economy if these solutions are accompanied by strong overarching policy recommendations that ensure barriers to scale are addressed, and enabling factors are enhanced. For example, in order to have a nature-based economy, nature-based solutions such as urban forestry and others that provide carbon sequestration need to be scaled immensely. However, these nature-based solutions find it difficult to attract private investors due to a lack of direct revenue streams that can be used to provide economic incentives to the private sector.

Hence nature-based solutions such as urban forestry need to be accompanied with policy amendments that address barriers such as providing more confidence in future revenue streams through greater certainty around carbon prices through for example a minimum price policy or framework for carbon. These policy amendments will increase confidence in commercially viable models and cash flows for nature-based solutions which in turn can help achieve scale and a transition to a nature-based economy.

Also, in addition to policy amendments that address barriers such as long-term revenue streams and commercially viable models, instruments and mechanisms that enhance the enabling factors at scale and incentivise nature-based solutions are essential. For example, BwB has worked closely with developing countries to develop and utilise KPI bonds (as well as SDG bonds found here: <https://www.bwbuk.org/post/bwb-partners-with-undp-to-issue-first-sdg-bond-for-uzbekistan>) that incentivise proceeds to be used for country-specific nature-based solutions that prioritise issues in each country. These KPI bonds, alongside a robust MRV (Monitoring, Reporting and Verification) mechanism allow for NBS projects to be implemented at scale given the significant coupon and principal reductions that can be achieved based on targets, hence the wider adoption of these instruments can have a more notable impact in terms of a nature-based economy. Another key enabling factor for achieving a nature-based economy will be mechanisms or frameworks put in place that correctly value NBS. BwB has developed a centralised mechanism named Green Neighbourhoods as a Service (found here: <https://www.bwbuk.org/post/green-neighbourhoods-as-a-service>) which utilises the co-benefits that arise from these projects to address the mismatch between ownership of the capital spend and of the value of benefits, tackle the fragmentation issue, overcome barriers to entry, allow aggregation of projects and matching of different types of finance that will be needed. Such a centralised mechanism that brings change on a neighbourhood-by-neighbourhood basis in the long-term can have a significant impact in achieving a nature-based economy.

Furthermore, in order for nature-based solutions to provide the basis for a nature-based economy, there needs to be greater transparency around the frameworks used to identify nature-based activities and ensure funder capital is directed to the correct coinciding projects. For example, the IUCN Global Standard provides clear parameters for defining nature-based solutions and a common framework to help benchmark progress. This is essential to increase the scale and impact of the NBS approach, prevent unanticipated negative outcomes or misuse, and help funding agencies, policy makers and other stakeholders assess the effectiveness of interventions. This will allow financiers to invest in NBS with confidence that the standard provides a benchmark, minimising risks and adding assurance. Such a standard also allows for the wider stakeholder groups in society to get involved and engage with the governance structure of the standard.

The extent to which nature-based solutions can provide a basis for a nature-based economy depends on the coinciding policies, frameworks and mechanisms implemented. With the correct policies that address barriers and drive enabling factors, nature-based solutions include such a wide variation of projects that they provide a strong foundation to achieve a nature based economy.

In conclusion, the extent to which nature-based solutions can provide a basis for a nature-based economy depends on the coinciding policies, frameworks and mechanisms implemented. With the correct policies that address barriers and drive enabling factors, nature-based solutions include such a wide variation of projects (including green and blue infrastructure, ecosystem services, ecosystem-based adaptation, ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction, blue-green infrastructure, low-impact development, best management practices, water-sensitive urban design, sustainable urban drainage systems and ecological engineering), that they provide a strong foundation to achieve a nature based economy, but not standalone.

About the Writer:
[David Maddox](#)

David loves urban spaces and nature. He loves creativity and collaboration. He loves theatre and music. In his life and work he has practiced in all of these.

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David Maddox

I worked for The Nature Conservancy in the late 1980s, and at that time significant money came to TNC from large corporate donations, with as car companies. A former president of the organization was asked if it was appropriate to use money to conserve land that was “tainted” by environmental damage by the donor in other sectors of the economy, especially extractive industries. He was famous for his answer, in American slang: “Tainted money? T’ain’t enough”. His meaning was that if we did good with the money, then its provenance was not a concern.

I am thrilled that some businesses are advancing in this conversation about sustainability. But we need more. We need everyone — all businesses and all people — to be part of the change, which will require sacrifice.

I and others were uncomfortable with this approach.

Our — meaning the world’s — issues of sustainability, resilience, livability, and social justice are so vast that the answers cannot be found in corporations donating to green causes, thus providing political cover. This is greenwashing. A coverup that simply happens to look green. Buried deep in our problem is that we are better at appearing to be green-virtuous than making fundamental changes that often are inconvenient or seem to “cost more”. This is for regular people too, not just businesses. Recycling comes to mind, when we recycle at higher rates, but consume even faster. We get a bigger car that has marginally better gas efficiency, but we drive more and don’t use public transportation. We buy organic food without worry that it was grown half way around the world.

These problems have roots in economies across sectors, from businesses themselves to people (i.e., consumers). Businesses, people, and governments will have to demand more of each other.

In the global north, where economies are largely grounded in an unsustainable demand for growth, we need to reassess our values, and both businesses and regular people will have to adapt and sacrifice by putting effort and money into change. Governments must help by creating real incentives to reward our efforts and regulations (such as planning and zoning codes and requirements for nature-based solutions) with bite.

In the global south we face a different but related challenge. It is that around the world millions of people need their standard of living raised. This will require greater consumption of food and energy, and will result in increases in factors that cause climate change. Many of us who read TNOC — most, I imagine — believe that raising living standards for the world’s underserved is moral, just, and right. Will we in the global north be prepared to sacrifice for this just cause? Maybe. Maybe not. For their part, all these new cities in the south are an opportunity to not repeat the same planning mistakes of current cities. We’ll need imagination, and resist the temptation of the easy solution that has a big development company (often from the north) get paid to recreate an old-fashioned solution.

- From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy -

I was one of several editors on a [book on about sustainability](#). It contained chapter by a journalist in Karachi, who wrote that the debates about sustainability and economies that occur in London and New York and Paris seem to occur on another planet, with no relevance to a city in which drinking water is sold on the street by organized crime. I shared the stage once with an indigenous (Mapuche) and women's right activist from Patagonia, hoc was also part of the aforementioned book. She recounted how she was challenged in Europe by a person with one child, who said the five children that the activist had were "immoral and unsustainable". The activist responded that her five children in Patagonia consumed many fewer resources that the accuser's one in Europe.

Fair enough. These are conversations that require action and often sacrifice. But whose sacrifice? They will be difficult conversations. They will require a willingness to acknowledge our own roles in the problems that face us.

For me, several imperatives are clear, although I am not sure people are ready for the political battles they would require. (I mean, we cannot seem to even agree that getting a vaccine is a good idea during a global heath crisis.)

- We need to abandon economic growth as a de-facto good
- We need to root out greenwashing
- We need to accept the idea that sustainability will cost all of us something
- We need to understand and act on (i.e., be responsible for) the true environmental costs and "footprint" of our actions
- Nature-based solutions should be required of all companies (and individuals when it makes sense), not just as a region-wide goal; and they can't just be another aspect of greenwashing
- We must achieve not carbon neutrality, but a carbon negative; this is the only way to sustain increased livability in developing nations

I am thrilled that some businesses are advancing in this conversation about sustainability. But we need more. We need everyone — all businesses and all people — to be part of the movement.

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Dr Audrey Timm is a horticultural scientist specialised in ornamental horticulture. Since joining International Association of Horticultural Producers (AIPH) as Technical Advisor in early 2019, Audrey leads their Green City initiative with the purpose of increasing the quality and quantity of living green in urban environments, and of nurturing a strategic shift in city form and function.

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Audrey Timm

The key to answering this question is in the word “solutions”. Nature-based-solutions need to solve a problem that challenges our quality of life in a way that makes them indispensable to our future.

In a broad conservation context, nature-based-solutions are very much about restoring natural systems to recover from or avert disasters. In a city context, we need to emulate natural systems. We need to understand how they work, and how this therefore provides the solution that we seek.

For example, trees capture rainfall, slow it down, and drip around the canopy fringe to support their own growth. By doing this trees protect the soil, both from reducing the impact of individual droplets that could compact the soil, and by preventing erosion from flooding. Leaf texture plays a role in rainfall interception, as does plant shape. Nature-based-solutions that aim to prevent flooding need to recognise this knowledge and use it to their advantage. Replacing hard, impermeable surfaces with planted and semi-permeable space doesn't stop heavy rainfall incidents occurring. It stops them from being a problem. The same is true with planted swales that are designed correctly and have suitable plants established. Other examples include hedges to buffer against noise pollution, green roofs and walls as thermal insulation, vegetation to attenuate local air pollution, and trees and greenery to reduce the urban heat island effect. All of these require an understanding of the characteristics of plants that deliver specific solutions, and of the selection and placement of plants in relation to the urban fabric to achieve success.

Nature-based-solutions in the urban environment go beyond simply providing an opportunity for reconnecting people and nature. They work in tandem with the built infrastructure, providing solutions that hard, engineered systems cannot deliver on their own. Implementing successful nature-based-solutions is driven not only by knowledge, but by an understanding of how the knowledge contributes to the solution. From this perspective, no single sector can drive a nature-based economy. When nature-based-solutions become an integral part of city infrastructure, nature becomes woven into the economic support network, providing new business opportunities, jobs and income-generating activities across a broad spectrum of the population. Nature-based-solutions cannot be motivated as part of the future of our city economies because nature needs our help; they are part of the economy because we need to mobilise the help of nature for our future.

When nature-based-solutions become an integral part of city infrastructure, nature becomes woven into the economic support network, providing new business opportunities, jobs and income-generating activities across a broad spectrum of the population.

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Cecilia Herzog

Let's invest in human incredible capacity and imagination to regenerate planet Earth

Yes, we urgently must adopt a nature-based economy worldwide. We need a radical shift in the indicators we measure value and wealth, and switch to an ecological economy. [Georgescu-Roegen](#), [Daly](#), [Elkington](#), [Klein](#), [McKibben](#), [Piketty](#), [Raworth](#), [Mazzucato](#), among so many others have been proposing and advocating for this essential transformation during the last century, especially in the last decades. The collapse we are now was foreseeable

long time ago. The present trigger is climate emergency showing that our environmental, social, and cultural predatory economy led us in a wrong direction. Countless concomitant climate impacts worldwide are happening. It is undeniable that time urges to transition to a new nature-based economy that fits in the planetary boundaries and reverse the abyssal social disparities, besides respecting social-cultural, ethnic, and gender distinctiveness of all people.

Climate is global and is affecting rich and poor countries, real people in the real world, destroying our biosphere on an unthinkable speed.

New green deals emerging in wealthy countries must take a tangible turn when NATURE and PEOPLE must be THE PRIORITY!

Brazil has a huge role to play in this scenario, where the AMAZON and other precious biomes collapse must be taken extremely seriously. At the Federal level things are going from bad to worse, to unimaginable catastrophic magnitude.

At city level, Brazilian cities are still introducing nature-based solutions as demonstration projects at a slow pace. The landscape transformation must gain scale urgently, bringing nature to all possible places. Taking out cars, planting trees and opening spaces for people close to regenerated urban nature, creating new and sustainable businesses and jobs.

Ecological education is key to everyone, introducing nature-based solutions in urban areas is an excellent way to enable urbanites to learn about ecological processes and our intrinsic relationship with all forms of life and how ecosystem services are essential to our own survival. We are in the decade of biodiversity, the protection of remnants and regeneration of degraded areas must be prioritized in all scales: gardens, ecosystems, biomes...

Multilateral banks are already focusing on NbS, inducing their investments to projects that are environmentally and socially oriented (e.g. [World Bank](#), [IDB](#)), as well as the [World Economic Forum](#). Many corporations are also at high risk, most of them depend on nature to produce their goods, sell their services and so on, and many are taking the questions seriously (e.g. [insurance companies](#)).

The [concentration of wealth in the hands of very few people](#) while the vast majority of the humanity tries to survive until the next meal, has to be addressed. In my view, there is no way we will overcome the disaster unless the economy, politics, and decision makers find a way to redistribute capital in a fair way, so every person on earth will be able to be concerned with our collective good and invest on nature-based solutions.

Brazilian cities are still introducing nature-based solutions as demonstration projects on a slow pace. The landscape transformation must gain scale urgently, bringing nature to all possible places. Taking out cars, planting trees and opening spaces for people close to regenerated urban nature, creating new and sustainable businesses and jobs.

The transformation of the way the economy functions must lead to innovative and creative ways to [regenerate nature](#) wherever possible, using our incredible capacity and imagination here on our planet Earth. For this to be achievable, it is also urgent to enlighten people to value nature (biodiversity, ecosystems, clean water bodies, oceans...) more than exploring other planets and buying superfluous consumer goods. We must innovate, educate, and create new jobs that restores ecosystems; produce healthy foods; build and prepare cities to be resilient to climate impacts; shift to clean and active mobility in comfortable and safe ways; adopt (incentivize) renewable energy (and divest on fossil fuel); value and invest in local production; besides developing technologies that enables recover ecological functions that are desperately needed.

I believe we will see a shift on the way we relate to nature so we can remain living on this wonderful planet that is our only home. This has been said so many times that all humans should be eager to contribute to enhance all forms of life, protect existent ecosystems (terrestrial and aquatic) and be trained to live and work on this new regenerative paradigm of nature-based economy.

About the Writer:

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Ana is a founder of the Centre for Experiments in Urban Studies (CEUS) from Belgrade, local coordinator of the CLEVER Cities project on urban regeneration via nature-based solutions, and PhD candidate in Spatial Planning.

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Ana Mitić-Radulović

Nature-based economy may be the critical window of opportunity

In the moment of absolutely obvious climate and environmental crisis — the summer of 2021 — the emerging concept of nature-based economy may be the critical window of opportunity for reversing the negative impacts of the current economic system, offering possible solutions for coping with the indispensable change ahead of us. Although nature-based solutions are perceived as enablers of “sustainable economic growth within the contexts of the climate change and biodiversity crises” (from Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy, a draft White Paper for Consultations, June 2021), today there are many reasons to question if “sustainable economic growth” is an oxymoron by itself. Nevertheless, the economy that “encompasses all production, exchange and consumption processes related to activities concerned with the protection, conservation, restoration and sustainable use of natural resources by consumers, industry and society at large” is by far the best option we can advocate for.

Post-pandemic recovery is the perfect occasion for spatial and urban planners to spark the conversation on grey-to-green transition of the public spaces and infrastructure, and for the governments to accept nature-based solutions and the accompanying economic activities, reskilling and upskilling of workers for green jobs, and adoption of policies which truly embrace nature-based economy.

One can argue that economic system which is sustainable cannot impose perpetual accumulation of the surplus capital. The encouraging news is that younger generations (Y and Z, millennials and post-millennials) seem to be aware of it and ready to give up on it, in return for natural and environmental protection, more social justice, human dignity, and preserved mental health.

Many environmental activists from these generations also refrain from opportunistic and anthropocentric monetizing and pricing of ecosystem services and from considering nature as an asset, claiming that nature is invaluable. However, underlining the economic potential of nature-based solutions and natural capital is indeed critical for their timely uptake and upscaling by governments and the private sector, necessary for the positive environmental impact we desperately need.

- From Nature-Based Solutions to the Nature-Based Economy -

Efforts to promote a nature-based economy, in order to triple the investments in nature-based solutions by 2030, must be twofold. To reach the targeted increase of 120 billion euros of private nature-based investments — from the current 15 billion (UN Report on the State of Finance for Nature, 2021) — it is inevitable to communicate, collaborate and co-create with powerful and impactful stakeholders. This stream of action can bring technical shifts and quicker quantitative results, valuable for the current moment and the post-pandemic recovery actions.

However, the profound value of nature-based economy and its potential for paradigm shift lies in the activities of the rising number of small, eco-social enterprises, that are not driven by necessarily creating the extra profit, but operating not-for-profit and environmentally responsible. This radical change of perception regarding satisfying, or even optimal business opportunities between the older generations (baby-boomers and Gen X) and the younger ones hopefully will bring qualitative, long-term transformation, serving as a cornerstone of restoration of our planet and protection of the organized human life on Earth that we know.

Social perspective of ecological transition is highly important: nature-based economy allows for new jobs, often less complex and more enjoyable, which can lead towards healthier and more just communities.

In the context of the Green Agenda for the Western Balkan, there is a strong potential for various sectors of nature-based enterprises in the EU Candidate Countries. Community landscape and biodiversity restoration has become fairly popular, as well as agritourism, regenerative agriculture and beekeeping. Demand for biomaterials for construction, green roofs and walls, as well as nature-based urban regeneration for urban green commons, green space management, and natural flood & surface water management are expected to develop in the near future. Challenges to uptake the nature-based economy in this area lie in the strong traditional engineering matrices and institutional impedance towards less technically-intensive, nature-based solutions.

Hemp home in Homolje Mountain, Serbia, Architects: Ljubica Arsić & Daniel Fuchs, Concept designer: Predrag Milosavljević; retrieved from [hempcity.co](#), on August 31, 2021.

Nevertheless, integrating urban perspective and the values of nature has never been more important. Post-pandemic recovery is the perfect occasion for spatial and urban planners to spark the conversation on grey-to-green transition of the public spaces and infrastructure, and for the governments to accept nature-based solutions and the accompanying economic activities, reskilling and upskilling of workers for green jobs, and adoption of policies which truly embrace nature-based economy.

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Domenico Vito

The European Commission defines nature based solutions as: "Solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience."

NBS mitigate and increase land value in all the four dimensions of sustainability: environmental, social, economical, and participative.

This definition contains several elements that resumes the main features and benefits related to nature based solutions. Nature based solutions (NBS) are forefront strategies for mitigation greenhouse gas emissions. Besides the best complex human technology, NBS collects with astonishing simplicity the benefits and the efficacy of act WITH nature rather than force nature against its rules. The impact of NBS is more holistic rather than reductionistic, as typical of the ones just technical or technological.

If these last ones are only acting on some of the sides of a problem that are intelligible by a model or a framework designed by humans, NBS are able to influence also ecological interactions, in a more integrated way. Compared also to just technological solution NBS bring a more pronounced participatory dimension. If technology is usual proprietary, market-based, owned, held by a company or entity, nature based solutions are collective, cooperative and community based. Just thinking to collective three planting. For these reasons NBS can be inserted into a context not only for their mitigation function, but also to regenerate lands on a social and economical dimension.

A clear example of such assumptions stands in agroforestry solutions. Agroforestry pushes to integrate agriculture with the local landscapes and biodiversity profiles. It is based on the principle of ecological succession, which wants to recreate the same relationships among plants, trees and grasses that persist in a vital forest. The added value is that together also food species are inserted. A case study of a virtuose agroforestry, that also provide economical and social benefits is the project "Milano Porta Verde" (see the images).

Sky Vision of Milano Porta Verde

In this project, 8 hectares of abandoned peri-urban land has been restored in collaboration with local association "Cascinet" and SoulFood Forest Farms Hub Italia". The area has been planted by the volunteers and local neighbours of Parco della Vettabbia with the agroforestry technique and a Community Supported Agriculture initiative with a partner farmer has been started.

Collective Replanting of 8 hectares at Vetrabbia Milan

So beside the ecological restoration, this area acquired a social and food chain value. Such an example is a clear demonstration of the second part of the definition of Nature Based Solutions, given that the EU that states “Such solutions bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions”.

Indeed, we can assume NBS mitigate and increase land value in all the four dimensions of sustainability: environmental, social, economical, and participative.